

Ranking and serial thinking: A geometric solution

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February 12, 2024

Abstract

A general mathematical description of the way the brain encodes ordinal knowledge of sequences is still lacking. Coherently with the well-established idea of mixed selectivity in high-dimensional state spaces, we conjectured the existence of a linear solution for serial learning tasks. In this theoretical framework, the neural representations of the items in a sequence are read out as ordered projections along a suited "geometric" mental line learned *via* classical conditioning (delta rule learning). We show that the derived model is capable of solving serial position tasks and explains all the behavioral effects observed in humans and other animal species performing the transitive inference task in the presence of noisy sensory information and stochastic neural activity. This result is generalized to the case of recurrent neural networks performing motor decisions, where the same geometric mental line is learned showing a tight correlation with the motor plan of the responses. Network activity is then eventually modulated according to the symbolic distance of presented item pairs, as observed in associative cortices of nonhuman primates. Serial ordering is thus predicted to emerge as a monotonic mapping between sensory input and behavioral output, highlighting a possible pivotal role of motor-related associative cortices in the transitive inference task.

1 Introduction

Serial thinking is a cognitive function underpinning almost any of our daily actions. Our brain continuously encodes temporal sequences that we can remember, process, and replay, such as the subsequent steps to make a sandwich or the path from home to work. Serial reasoning underlies logical deduction, categorical and hierarchical thinking, which are crucial to many higher-level cognitive functions (episodic memory, algebraic computation, language, and many others). A still widely open challenge is to find a unique framework in which all these different abilities could be explained, and several hypotheses about how sequences are mentally encoded have been proposed [1, 2].

One of these hypotheses is that sequence information in serial learning tasks is represented in the brain as an ordinal knowledge of the items in the list, independently from their timing or their spatial location. The ranking of the elements of a sequence based on the assigned order implies an abstraction of their arrangement, together with the simultaneous encoding of the ordinal and item-specific information [3, 4]. Notably, these are the building blocks of a more general framework named 'compositional computation' [5, 6].

Task-relevant information, such as ordinal knowledge in serial thinking, is typically encoded by resorting to specific neuronal representations in the high dimensional state spaces of their activity. These representations in the brain are sparse and involve relatively wide populations of neurons [7, 8]. The high degree of dynamical complexity expressed by such neuronal networks can be exploited to solve relatively difficult cognitive tasks by simply resorting to a linear mapping of their collective neuronal states [9, 10, 11].

Within this theoretical framework, we conjecture the existence of a geometrical solution for serial learning tasks associated with the reorganization of a specific neuronal subspace. This manifold is a line where the arbitrary elements of a sequence can be ranked in any order as suited projections of their neural representations. We derive

44 its analytical form hypothesizing it is the so-called ‘mental line’ capable of solving serial ordering tasks [12, 13, 14,
 45 15]. The proposed ‘geometric mental line’ (GML) is capable of explaining all the behavioral effects observed in
 46 Humans and other animals performing an implicit serial learning task, the so-called Transitive Inference (TI) task
 47 [16, 17]. We found that the noisy representation of the stimuli to be ordered plays an important role in learning and
 48 shaping the behavioral performances. Our GML is embedded in the low-dimensional space determined by the
 49 neural states encoding the items in a sequence, and it turns out to be naturally implemented in recurrent neural
 50 networks (RNN). In this framework, the dynamical drift along the GML determining behavioral output results to be
 51 an attractive manifold where single units are strongly correlated, further reducing the dimensionality of the latent
 52 state space where the neural activity unfolds.

53 2 Results

54 2.1 Ranking abstract items: The geometric mental line

55 Consider for example $M = 4$ items $S_1 = ‘A’$, $S_2 = ‘B’$, $S_3 = ‘C’$ and $S_4 = ‘D’$. Arbitrarily ranking this set of items
 56 means to put them in sequences like ‘ABCD’ or ‘CADB’, eventually assigning to each S_k the chosen rank $r_k \in \mathbb{Z}$,
 57 with index $k \in [1, M]$. In the former example we then have $\{r_k\}_{k=1}^M = \{4, 3, 2, 1\}$, while in the latter the ranks are
 58 $\{3, 1, 4, 2\}$. A typical example with $M = 7$ often used in cognitive neuroscience is shown in Fig. 1a. Given that,
 59 what kind of computational capabilities must a network of neurons be equipped with to solve this task? In other
 60 words, what is the machinery needed to encode the generic rank of a set of items?

Figure 1: **Item representations and the geometric mental line (GML).** **a**, An example list of $M = 7$ abstract items S_k here represented as letters (‘A’, ‘B’, ...) with rank r_k such that the k -th item is greater than S_j only if $r_k > r_j$. **b**, A shallow network (linear Perceptron) with N neurons (orange circles) with activity x_i ($i \in [1, N]$) linearly modulated by the presentation of one of the M items in (a). The k -isolated item elicits the neural state $|x\rangle = |S_k\rangle$, which in turn is read out as a projection on the GML $\langle \zeta |$ returning the rank r_k . Such projection is given by the inner product $\langle \zeta | x \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N \zeta_i x_i$ of the Perceptron state and the read-out synaptic weights $\zeta_i = \{\langle \zeta | \}_i$ determining the GML. **c,d**, Two example sequences with different ordering of three abstract items ‘A’, ‘B’ and ‘C’ with the related GML $\langle \zeta |$ given by Eq. (3). Each item representation lies on the orthogonal axes $|S_k\rangle$. Their projections (colored points on the GML) are differently sorted depending on the GML orientation. **e**, Same as (c) but considering a sensory (‘directional’) noise $|\xi_n\rangle$ in the item representation that now at each trial n (colored dots) are mildly displaced from the corresponding $|S_k\rangle$. As a result, projections on the GML will be distributed around the expected rank r_k (colored distributions).

61 To address this question, we start considering that, under stationary conditions, a network of neurons can

62 represent a stimulus (i.e., one of the items S_k) as a vector in the space of neuronal states. Referring to the
 63 rate-coding framework, this representation corresponds to the set $|S_k\rangle = |x\rangle$ of firing rates x_i that the N neurons
 64 ($i \in [1, N]$) have in response to such stimulation (Fig. 1b). For the sake of simplicity here $|S_k\rangle \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is a
 65 column vector where the i -th element $\{|S_k\rangle\}_i = S_{ki}$ can be both positive or negative. As such, neural activity x_i
 66 represents the change of firing rate of the i -th neuron in a shallow network like a linear Perceptron [18, 19].

67 In associative cortices, neurons respond to different stimuli with a ‘mixed’ selectivity [20, 21, 7]. Mixed coding
 68 implies input decorrelation enabling the flexible storage of relations between items [22], and it is naturally imple-
 69 mented by introducing a layer of randomly connected neurons [23, 7]. According to this, we assume that the inner
 70 representations $|S_k\rangle$ are independent random vectors such that for any $j, k \in [1, M]$

$$\langle S_j | S_k \rangle \equiv \sum_{i=1}^N S_{ji} S_{ki} = \delta_{jk}. \quad (1)$$

71 Here, according to the ‘bra-ket’ notation adopted in quantum mechanics [24], $\langle S_j |$ is a row vector given by trans-
 72 posing $|S_j\rangle$. $\langle S_j | S_k \rangle$ is the inner product returning the projection of the vector $|S_k\rangle$ onto the axis defined by $\langle S_j |$.
 73 This condition naturally holds in the limit of $N \rightarrow \infty$, provided that S_{ki} are independent random activities with
 74 zero mean and variance $1/N$. In this limit, Eq. (1) tells us that the set of M states $|S_k\rangle$ are an orthogonal basis
 75 (i.e., the axes) of an M -dimensional subspace living in the full N -dimensional neural state-space (Fig. 1c).

76 In this modeling framework, a linear readout unit (the gray circle in Fig. 1b) returning the arbitrary function
 77 $f(r_k)$ of the rank r_k assigned to the k -th item,

$$f(r_k) = \langle \zeta | S_k \rangle, \quad (2)$$

78 exists and it is given by the following linear combination of item representations:

$$\langle \zeta | = \sum_{j=1}^M f(r_j) \langle S_j |. \quad (3)$$

79 Indeed, from this definition $\langle \zeta | S_k \rangle = \sum_{j=1}^M f(r_j) \langle S_j | S_k \rangle = \sum_{j=1}^M f(r_j) \delta_{jk} = f(r_k)$ proving Eq. (2) for any set of
 80 assigned ranks $\{r_k\}_{k=1}^M$. Note that by adding to the GML any arbitrary vector $\langle \gamma |$ external to the M -dimensional
 81 space (i.e., $\langle \gamma | S_k \rangle = 0$ for any k), Eq. (2) still holds leaving unchanged the model output. This means that in
 82 principle an infinite number of GML exist. We will come back on this point later in the text.

83 In the particular case $f(r_k) = r_k$, the row vector of synaptic weights $\langle \zeta |$ allows to readout directly the rank
 84 of the k -th item presented to the shallow network in Fig. 1b. It results to be proportional to the projection of
 85 the network state $|x\rangle$ along the line oriented as $\langle \zeta |$, as shown in Fig. 1c for the example sequence ‘ABC’. Here,
 86 although $\langle \zeta |$ is the vector of synaptic weights between the readout y and the units x_i , we can represent it as a
 87 line in the network state-space. Indeed, from Eq. (3) $\langle \zeta |$ is a weighted sum of the network activities $|x\rangle = |S_k\rangle$
 88 leading to interpret it also as an activity pattern itself. In this geometric framework, the model output (i.e., the
 89 inner product $y = \langle \zeta | x \rangle = \sum_j \zeta_j x_j$) explicitly corresponds to the projection of the network state onto the line $\langle \zeta |$.
 90 The geometrically composed $\langle \zeta |$ is then the searched mental line where item representation are sorted solving a
 91 serial ordering task. As such, in what follows we call $\langle \zeta |$ the ‘geometric mental line’ (GML). Changing item order
 92 from ‘ABC’ to ‘BCA’ as in Fig. 1d, the GML rotates in the $M = 3$ -dimensional space of the representations $|S_k\rangle$
 93 giving a new set of projections sorted according to the new item position in the sequence.

94 Now we consider the fact that the neural state encoding an item is unavoidably noisy. This because the units
 95 activities x_i in a network fluctuate due to several sources of ‘thermal’ noise, which we will refer to as endogenous
 96 noise. Indeed, these units aim at modeling cortical cell assemblies composed of a finite number of neurons,
 97 each receiving balanced excitatory and inhibitory currents [25, 26]. Another source of stochasticity is the sensory
 98 (‘directional’) noise affecting the input received by the network when items are presented. This effect takes into
 99 account the fact that item representations are corrupted due to a change of the attentional level, for instance, or a
 100 temporary partial view of the visual stimuli. In this case the actual input received by the network can be modeled
 101 as $|S_k\rangle + |\xi_n\rangle$, where the column vector $|\xi_n\rangle$ is a random perturbation occurring at the trial n , affecting in turn the
 102 direction of the item representation. As shown in Fig. 1e, the result of this sensory noise is that in each trial the
 103 item lies in a different position close to its uncorrupted representation $|S_k\rangle$. The resulting projections on the GML
 104 will be then distributed around the rank r_k with variance $\sigma_S^2 = \sum_{n=1}^T \langle \zeta | \xi_n \rangle^2 / T$ estimated across the T trials per

105 item presented. Thus, even under this noisy condition, the GML in Eq. (3) solves on average the serial ordering task.
 106 task.

107 As we will see later, the stochasticity of both network activity and item representations is a key ingredient to
 108 explain the wide set of behavioral effects observed in serial learning tasks.

109 2.2 The Transitive Inference task: learning the GML

110 Transitive inference (TI) is an implicit serial reasoning task, which consists in generalizing the comparison between
 111 items based on an arbitrary assigned rank in a sequence. In particular, knowing how adjacent items relate to
 112 each other (i.e., $A > B$, $B > C$), the relationship among stimuli never compared before can be inferred (i.e., $A > C$).
 113 Together with Humans, plenty of animal species have been found to show such an ability: birds, rodents, fishes
 114 and non-human primates [27, 28]. Successfully performing a TI task thus means having encoded the order of the
 115 presented items. Is this ordering computed relying on the same GML derived in Eq. (3)?

Figure 2: **The GML solves the transitive inference task.** **a**, The pairs of adjacent items (with their relationship) presented on a screen during the first learning phase of the task. **b**, Example trial of transitive inference (TI) task. Once a pair (BA) is presented on the screen, after the Go signal (disappearance of the red cue) the subject chooses to move to the right touching the item with the highest rank (i.e., A). If the choice is correct as in this case, the subject eventually receives a reward. **c**, Shallow network as in Fig. 1 responding to the presentation of the pair 'BA' with a positive readout ($y = 1$) instructs to touch the right item ('A' with the highest rank as $r_1 = 7 > r_2 = 6$). The representation $|S_k\rangle$ of the presented items ($k \in \{1, 2\}$) are linearly combined as input to the network unit with arbitrary $+1$ and -1 for the right and the left position, respectively. Readout unit y is given by the projection of the network state onto the GML $\langle \zeta |$. **d**, In the presence of items corrupted by sensory noise the state vectors $|S_j - S_k\rangle$ (pointed out by a pair of light gray lines) appear as a distribution of perturbed states (dots). Once projected onto the GML (the gray line $\langle \zeta |$), they give rise to Gaussian-distributed readouts centered around the expected signed symbolic distances (SD), which for the example trials 'BA', 'DB' and 'AD' shown are 1, 2 and -3 . **e**, Pairs of items presented during the test phase (top) and the expected distributions of readout activity y of the shallow network in (c) (bottom). The network 'response' y is given by the projection of the GML worked out relying only on the item pairs from the learning set (a).

116 To answer this question, we consider as workbench a standard non-verbal TI task, with a list of $M = 7$ visual
 117 stimuli, conventionally associated with the letters from 'A' to 'G' and ordered alphabetically as in Fig. 1a. During
 118 the learning phase of the task, only pairs of adjacent items (e.g., 'AB', 'BC', 'CD', ...) are presented on a screen

119 during different trials (Fig. 2a). Following the appearance of the pair, the subject is required to choose the item
 120 with the highest rank (Fig. 2b). If the item, chosen after a reaction time, is correct, a reward is received.

121 The shallow network in Fig. 2c implements this task by linearly combining the inner representations $|S_k\rangle$ of the
 122 pair of items appearing on the screen. Coefficients of the combination are arbitrarily set to $+1$ and -1 to account
 123 for the right and left location of the items, respectively, leading to the network state $|x\rangle = |S_k\rangle - |S_j\rangle \equiv |S_k - S_j\rangle$.
 124 The readout unit $y = \langle \zeta | x \rangle$ will inform to reach the right or the left item by responding $+1$ or -1 , respectively.
 125 We now ask whether a vector, in the M -dimensional subspace of the item representations, $\langle \zeta | = \sum_{n=1}^M a_n \langle S_n |$
 126 with suited real a_n can solve the task. The set of coefficients a_n should be found taking into account only the
 127 learning set of pairs, where the ranks of the presented items always differ by one: $|r_k - r_j| = 1$. Recalling now
 128 Eq. (1), the response to a generic pair of items $|S_k\rangle, |S_j\rangle$ results to be $y = \langle \zeta | x \rangle = \sum_{n=1}^M a_n \langle S_n | S_k - S_j \rangle =$
 129 $\sum_{n=1}^M a_n (\delta_{nk} - \delta_{nj}) = a_k - a_j$. This implies that for any arbitrary coefficient a_n holds the relationship $a_k - a_j =$
 130 $r_k - r_j \in \{+1, -1\}$ for all item pairs in the learning set (which is composed of pairs with adjacent items, i.e., with
 131 $|SD| = 1$). This is a linear system of $M - 1$ equations with M unknown variables a_k having an infinite number of
 132 solutions $a_k = r_k + \varphi$, with φ any arbitrary real number. Hence, the shallow network solves the TI task with

$$\langle \zeta | = \sum_{k=1}^M r_k \langle S_k | + \varphi \sum_{k=1}^M \langle S_k | . \quad (4)$$

133 This solution is the same as the GML in Eq. (3) with $f(r_k) = r_k + \varphi$. Notably, this family of mental lines gives the
 134 right output choice even when the test set of item pairs (unseen during learning) is presented. Indeed, due to the
 135 orthonormality of item representations in Eq. (1), the readout results to be

$$y = \langle \zeta | S_k - S_j \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^M (r_i + \varphi) (\delta_{ik} - \delta_{ij}) = r_k - r_j , \quad (5)$$

136 which is the so called ‘symbolic distance’ ($SD = r_k - r_j$) giving for any pair $\{S_k, S_j\}$ the response to move to the
 137 rightmost item if $y > 0$, i.e., if $r_k > r_j$. Of course if $y < 0$ the item to choose is the one on the left. The learning
 138 set of pairs then allows in principle to find the GML solving both the TI task and the serial ordering task introduced
 139 in the previous Sect. 2.1. Here it is important to remark that the particular map $f(r_k) \propto r_k$ is tightly related to the
 140 specific learning protocol adopted in the TI task. Indeed, if a different set of item pairs would be presented during
 141 learning or the amount of reward would depend on the serial position of the involved items, $f(r_k) \not\propto r_k$ would
 142 result in Eq. (4), as we show later in detail.

143 Notably, the same GML allows to readout another relevant quantity in the TI task: the ‘joint rank’ [29] $JR =$
 144 $r_k + r_j$, i.e., the sum of the ranks of the two presented items. Indeed, by summing the item representation the
 145 readout unit gives

$$\langle \zeta | S_k + S_j \rangle = r_k + r_j + 2\varphi , \quad (6)$$

146 which in the general case of $\varphi \neq 0$ leads to have projections on the GML containing a biased estimate of the joint
 147 rank.

148 Note that in the subspace of the item representations, pairs of items are no more aligned to the $|S_k\rangle$ ‘axis’.
 149 Indeed, as shown in Fig. 2d, their representation $|S_k - S_j\rangle$ bisect the plane determined by $|S_k\rangle$ and $|S_j\rangle$ of the two
 150 presented items. Considering now the sensory noise previously introduced, these representations are randomly
 151 distributed as a cloud centered in $|S_k - S_j\rangle$. This because in a given trial n , the actual representation of the pair
 152 will be $|x\rangle = |S_k + \xi_n^{(R)}\rangle - |S_j + \xi_n^{(L)}\rangle$. As in Sect. 2.1, the representational noises of left ($|\xi_n^{(L)}\rangle$) and right ($|\xi_n^{(R)}\rangle$)
 153 items once projected on the GML are independent random variables with mean $\mathbb{E}[\langle \zeta | \xi_n^{(R,L)} \rangle] = 0$ and variance
 154 $\mathbb{V}[\langle \zeta | \xi_n^{(R,L)} \rangle] = \sigma_\xi^2$. Hence, the readout of noisy pairs is $y = \langle \zeta | S_k - S_j \rangle + \langle \zeta | \xi_n^{(R)} - \xi_n^{(L)} \rangle = r_k - r_j + \sqrt{2}\sigma_\xi \Gamma_n$,
 155 where in each trial n , Γ_n is an independent random Gaussian variable with zero mean and unit variance. One
 156 example pair from the learning set (‘BA’ with $SD = +1$) and two pairs from the test set (‘AD’ and ‘DB’ with $SD = -3$
 157 and $+2$, respectively) are shown Fig. 2d, together with the expected Gaussian distribution of the readout symbolic
 158 distances.

159 The distributions of readouts for all the item pairs (i.e., from both learning and test set) are shown in Fig. 2e. In
 160 agreement with the so-called ‘symbolic distance effect’ (SDE) [30], pairs with large $|SD|$ lead our shallow network
 161 to respond correctly with higher probability. This is because the related Gaussian distribution of the readout y
 162 is far from the origin. In contrast, the likelihood of making a mistake increases with decreasing symbolic distance,

163 as the chance to have a readout with the opposite sign of the rank difference (i.e., $(r_k - r_j)y < 0$) widens. The
 164 arrangement of these distributions also supports another well-documented behavioral effect. In fact, first and last
 165 item distributions are less overlapped with the others compared to what happens to the distributions of central
 166 items. This leads, in principle, to higher performances for the pairs containing terminal items, namely the ‘serial
 167 position effect’ (SPE) detailed in the following Section.

168 2.3 Learning the serial order of noisy items

169 Although a geometric mental line can be inferred by observing only the pairs of adjacent items in a sequence, and
 170 it works on average also in the presence of sensory noise, can it be learned in a shallow network of linear units?
 171 Previous modeling efforts investigated such possibility proving that this is the case in single-layer networks of
 172 formal neurons trained with a ‘delta rule’ [31, 32]. Delta rule learning [33, 34] is equivalent to classical conditioning
 173 in behavioral psychology [35, 34] as it reinforces the network weights minimizing the mean square error between
 174 expected and actual responses. The learned weights $\langle \zeta \rangle$ are then those resulting from a least mean squares
 175 algorithm which can be directly computed from the pseudoinverse of the network activity across trials [36].

Figure 3: **Learning the mental line from the TI task.** **a**, Accuracy is the fraction of correct responses y , i.e., those pointing to the item with highest rank ($ySD > 0$). **b**, Response accuracy after learning with varying levels of sensory noise σ_S for item pairs grouped by symbolic distance SD. **c**, Symbolic distance effect (SDE) at varying σ_S . The accuracy in (b) is averaged across pairs grouped by SD in absolute value (i.e., by the easiness of the task $|SD|$). **d**, Serial position effect (SPE) obtained as in (c) but averaging across items. **e**, Post-learning average readout activity $y = \langle \zeta_L | x \rangle$ for different SDs and noise levels. Dashed line, y resulting from the theoretical GML ($\sigma_S = 0$). **f**, Overlaps between theoretical $\langle \zeta \rangle$ and learned $\langle \zeta_L \rangle$ mental lines, i.e., the cosine of the angle $\widehat{\zeta_L}$. The simulated network (Fig. 2c) has $N = 1000$ units. The $M = 7$ items have sensory noise $\sigma_S / \sqrt{N} = \{0.05, 0.10, 0.15\}$. Task sessions have $T / (M - 1) = 25$ trials per pair of adjacent items, and for each noise level σ_S , 20 random sessions are simulated. Weights $\langle \zeta_L \rangle$ for each session are computed from the pseudoinverse of the network activity across the $T = 150$ trials (see Methods). Response accuracy of the learned $\langle \zeta \rangle$ is estimated for each item pair by extracting 10^5 random realizations of the sensory noise. Box plots in (f) represent the distribution of results across the 20 simulated sessions.

176 Following this approach, we computed the learned $\langle \zeta_L \rangle$ in our network performing the TI task in Fig. 2 with
 177 noisy pairs of adjacent items, and varying the presented pairs randomly from trial to trial (see Methods). As
 178 expected, the response accuracy (i.e., the fraction of correct responses, Fig. 3a) measured after learning depends
 179 on both the difficulty of the task, the level of noise and the rank of involved items (Fig. 3b) [31, 32]. For sufficiently
 180 high noise σ_S , performances increase with the symbolic distance ($|SD|$) between items, giving rise in Fig. 3c to

181 the SDE introduced before. Similarly, U-shaped performances arise only for large enough σ_S displaying higher
 182 accuracies for pairs containing terminal items of the sequence Fig. 3d. This is the mentioned SPE associated with
 183 the fact that first and last items are the ones always winning and losing, respectively, and thus they are easier to
 184 discriminate. From these results, a suitable noise level $\sigma_S \simeq 0.15\sqrt{N}$ allows for the reproduction of experimental
 185 psychometric functions measured, for instance, in monkeys [37, 30, 38, 27, 39, 40].

186 Inspecting the distribution of responses $y = \langle \zeta_L | x \rangle$ across trials with varying difficulty (Fig. 3e), we found that
 187 the learned mental line is still a geometric combination of the mean representation of the items. Indeed, a linear
 188 relationship between readout activity and symbolic distance is apparent although the slope of the regression now
 189 decreases with σ_S . This is because the learned GML $\langle \zeta_L |$ is no longer parallel to the theoretical one from Eq. (3)
 190 (Fig. 3f). In fact, the noisy representations $|S_k + \xi_n\rangle$ averaged across the presented trials are not fully embedded
 191 into the M -dimensional space of the exact representations $|S_k\rangle$ where the theoretical GML unfolds. Thus, the
 192 larger is the noise σ_S , the smaller is the overlap between these subspaces, meaning that the network state falls
 193 in large part into the orthogonal $N - M$ -dimensional space. As a consequence, the representations of items
 194 $|S_k + \xi_n\rangle$ only in part are embedded in the subspace occupied by the learned GML, leading to y values linearly
 195 distributed on a range that shrinks with the noise level.

196 2.4 Nonlinear mapping of serial order depends on task protocol

197 In the previous Section, we have shown that the encoding ‘quality’ of the items to sort, eventually affects the
 198 shape of the GML, and hence, the projections y determining the behavior. Indeed, learning in the presence
 199 of higher sensory noise reduces the quality of the item representations leading to a GML oriented in directions
 200 external to the M -dimensional space of the items (Fig. 3e,f). The quality of such representations can in general
 201 be influenced also by the design of the task and the cognitive resources requested to solve it. An example is the
 202 ‘immediate serial recall’ (ISR) task [41, 42, 43] consisting in the presentation of a sequence of items, followed by
 203 a test phase in which the subject is requested to recall such items in the same order they have been seen. ISR
 204 task is performed in this test phase by accessing the short-term memory (STM) of the items with their position in
 205 the sequence. The limited amount of cognitive/neuronal resources for STM limits the length of the sequence to
 206 reproduce [44, 45]. According to ‘ordinal theories’, this can be modeled with a decreasing activation of the item
 207 representations in memory [46, 47, 41].

208 Here, to implement this effect in our GML model (i.e, the shallow network in Fig. 1), we consider items as
 209 ‘corrupted’ by an amount of sensory noise which increases with their rank (Fig. 4a-right). This is an alternative way
 210 to modulate the strength of the item representations in the sequence according to their position. As a result, the
 211 first items have a stronger representation (i.e., higher quality) than the last ones, being less corrupted by sensory
 212 noise, similar to what was observed in the prefrontal cortex of monkeys performing a serial movement task [48].
 213 Sensory noise σ_S is linearly modulated according to the serial position k of the item: $\sigma_S(k) = \sigma_S(1) + \beta(k - 1)$.
 214 In this framework, β is the rate of STM resources used per item. It thus determines the corruption degree of the
 215 item representations which increases with the length of a sequence. As in the previous Section, we then compute
 216 the learned GML $\langle \zeta |$ from a random sequence of items $|S_k + \xi_n\rangle$ with representational noise $|\xi_n\rangle$ having standard
 217 deviation $\sigma_S(k)$ given by the serial position k (see Methods). Model performances are tested by recalling multiple
 218 times the same sequence of items, as in the single-trial version of the ISR [47]. By increasing the corruption
 219 rate β , the readout $y = \langle \zeta | S_k + \xi_n \rangle$ averaged across sequences, displays a saturation (Fig. 4a-left) leading to
 220 a no longer linear dependence on the order k , and thus on the item rank r_k (i.e., $y \propto f(r_k)$ rather than $\propto r_k$).
 221 Remarkably, in our model such nonlinearity emerges although it operates only linear transformations of sensory
 222 representations with the GML given again by Eq. (3).

223 Considering now the behavioral response in the modeled ISR task as given by the nearest serial position to the
 224 readout y (recall is not multiple choices as in [46], see Methods), we measure from the simulations the fraction
 225 of sequences reporting for each item a wrongly assigned position/rank (Fig. 4b). For a given corruption rate,
 226 the number of errors shows a non-monotonic pattern, highlighting the coexistence of the so-called ‘primacy’ and
 227 ‘recency’ effects [42, 49, 41, 50]. For the former effect, the first item in the sequence has the highest performances.
 228 Performances then decrease with serial position k , as the item representations in the model have corruption
 229 degrees increasing with k . Differently, the recency effect occurs when the last item is better remembered than
 230 the second-last. In the model, this happens because the readouts exceeding the maximum rank have always as
 231 their nearest serial position the length of the sequence. It is intriguing to note that, as β increases, error curves
 232 grow and widen their concavity similarly to what found in ISR experiments involving verbal items with varying

Figure 4: **Nonlinear mapping of serial positions and ranks.** **a**, Average readout of $M = 6$ items stored in short-term memory (STM) to perform an immediate serial-recall (ISR) task. Model network and GML learning as in Fig. 3 but receiving only one item per time. Representations of items to recall have sensory noise $\sigma_S(k) = \sigma_S(1) + \beta(k - 1)$, linearly increasing with the position k in the sequence. For each corruption rate β , 100 trials per item are simulated. GML is learned requiring the readout to give the position of the represented item ($y = \langle \zeta | x \rangle = k$). Right, distribution of readouts per item for $\beta = 0.0075$ and 0.12 from 10^4 trials post learning. **b**, Fraction of trials wrongly assigning the order of a specific item at different corruption rates. Item order in the model is given by the serial position between 1 and M nearest to the readout y . **c**, Fraction of tested sequences with different length M perfectly recalled at varying β . A perfect recall occurs when the serial positions of all the M items are correctly readout by the model with learned GML. **d**, Average readout in the same model network learning to perform the TI task as in Fig. 3 but with a probabilistic reward schedule. The correct choice in each trial is only randomly assigned to the item with the highest rank. The probability that the highest item is the one to choose, decreases logarithmically with its position k (see Methods). Such decrease is modulated by the scaling parameter σ . $\sigma = 0$ implies no bias (standard TI task, right-top), while $\sigma = 0.35$ (right-bottom) determines an increased probability of switching the correct choice. **e-f**, Mean accuracy per symbolic distance and per item (i.e., serial position), respectively, for varying σ in the test phase.

233 phonological similarity [42].

234 The GML framework allows to describe also the ‘list-length effect’ (Fig. 4c). Indeed, the fraction of sequences
 235 recalled without errors in ISR experiments decreases with the number of items composing the list, eventually
 236 giving rise to an inverted sigmoid [43, 47]. The higher the corruption rate, the lower the performances in our
 237 model, shifting to left (i.e., perfect recall only for shorter lists) the psychometric function, similarly to what is found

in experiments where different sensory modalities (visual or auditory) are taken into account [43].

Serial order in the ISR task with strength modulation of the item representation is not the only way to learn a nonlinear mapping of the position in the sequence onto the GML. Indeed, the same nonlinearity can arise in the TI task solved in our framework just by changing the reward schedule. For an ‘unbiased’ reward not depending on the rank, we have shown in Fig. 3e,f that the linear map (i.e., $y = f(r_k) \propto r_k$) naturally emerges. We now adopt a ‘biased’ schedule for which in randomly selected trials the choice of the lower-rank item in the pair is rewarded. More specifically, if the pair $\{S_k, S_{k\pm 1}\}$ appears on the screen we no longer consider correct the response given by $r_k - r_{k\pm 1} = \pm 1$. Rather, on each trial we assign a random rank \tilde{r}_k to each of the two items, sampled from Gaussian distributions with mean $\log(r_k)$ and standard deviation σ . Here, σ determines the scaling factor of this logarithmically biased schedule. In this way the correct response is determined by the sign of the random variable given by the difference of the extracted ranks, having itself a Gaussian distribution with mean $\log r_k - \log r_{k\pm 1} = -\log(1 \mp 1/r_k)$ and standard deviation $\sqrt{2}\sigma$ (see Methods).

In simulations, learning in biased TI task leads to a GML given by Eq. (3) with projections displaying a logarithmic trend (Fig. 4d). This trend becomes even more apparent with increasing scaling factor σ . Of course, if the reward value is deterministically assigned ($\sigma = 0$), the standard TI task is recovered and the readout returns to be linear: $f(r_k) \propto r_k$. Intriguingly, the ‘behavioral’ performances of the model are only mildly affected by such a drastic rotation of the GML leading to an almost unchanged SDE (Fig. 4e). This is not the case for the SPE (Fig. 4f), as the U-shaped pattern of the mean accuracy per item becomes more asymmetric being skewed towards higher ranks. As the rank determines the serial position in the list of items, the asymmetry in the SPE qualitatively replicates what is shown in Fig. 4b for the ISR task, further strengthening the hypothesis of a common GML-based ranking mechanism.

2.5 Serial ordering in recurrent neural networks

So far, we solved the transitive inference task relying on a simple one-layer pool of uncoupled units whose activity is readout by a linear Perceptron with weights given by Eq. (3). However, cortical networks have recurrent synaptic connections and the firing rate $x_i(t)$ of their units is intrinsically stochastic. In this more realistic framework, can the same geometric mental line be used to compute the arbitrary rank assigned to the items of a sequence? To answer this question we consider a recurrent neural network (RNN) with units coupled *via* a random connectivity matrix and each receiving a stochastic input current intended to model an endogenous source of noise (see Methods). As for the shallow network in Fig. 2c, the RNN receives as additional input the representations of the items simultaneously presented in pairs (Fig. 5a). Even in this network model, the activity $|x\rangle$ is readout as a projection onto the GML ($y = \langle \zeta | x \rangle$).

Under the hypothesis of relatively weak recurrent connections, the dynamics of the network state $|x\rangle$ can be linearized giving rise to the following stochastic differential equation for the readout unit (see Methods):

$$\tau dy = (-y + \text{SD}) dt + \sigma_E dW, \quad (7)$$

which turns out to be a leaky integrator driven by a Gaussian white noise $dW(t)$ with zero mean and covariance dt , an infinitesimal time step [51]. Here τ is the relaxation time scale of the network units and σ_E is the size of the endogenous noise affecting each unit of the network. Here, the distribution of the readout activity exponentially adapts to a Gaussian distribution centered around the symbolic distance SD between the presented items (Fig. 5b), thus RNN can solve the TI task relying on the same GML derived above.

In this modeling framework, the RNN readout can play the role of the ‘decision value’ in diffusive models of perceptual decision [52]. Accordingly, the decision to reach the right (left) item on the screen is taken when the threshold level $+\theta$ ($-\theta$) is crossed by $y(t)$ for the first time Fig. 5b [31]. For such a decision process, the accuracy (i.e., the probability of crossing the correct decision threshold and thus making the right choice) and the reaction time (i.e., the time RT when $|y(\text{RT})| > \theta$ for the first time starting from $y(0) = 0$) can be analytically derived for $\theta \ll 1$. Indeed, in this limit Eq. (7) is well approximated by a Wiener process with two ‘absorbing’ barriers [51]. For it the probability to have $y(t)$ crossing the positive threshold θ when $\text{SD} = r_R - r_L > 0$ is given by

$$\alpha(\text{SD}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \tanh \frac{\theta \text{SD}}{\sigma_E^2} \right). \quad (8)$$

This accuracy is an estimate of the fraction of correct trials where the item on the right is chosen as having the highest rank. Similarly to what was found for shallow networks in the presence of sensory noise in Fig. 3c, the

Figure 5: **TI task in a recurrent neural network (RNN).** **a**, Configuration of an RNN composed of N units with stochastic activity x_i ($i \in [N]$) and random connectivity matrix, modeling a cortical network capable of solving the TI task. The weights of synapses between pairs of units are randomly sampled from a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and standard deviation g/\sqrt{N} . The coupling strength is assumed to be weak ($g \ll 1$) leading to a linearized dynamics of $x_i(t)$. As in Fig. 2c, the pair of items presented during a trial provides an input with strength g_S given by the difference $g_S |S_R - S_L\rangle$ between right and left item representations, respectively. The activity randomness is driven by a ‘thermal’ white noise (endogenous noise) received by the network unit as an independent input with the same fluctuation size. As in the example shallow networks, the activity $|x(t)\rangle$ is readout by the unit $y = \langle \zeta | x \rangle$. The vector of weights $\langle \zeta |$ is the GML defined by Eq. (3) with $f(r_k) = r_k$ rescaled in this case by a factor $1/g_S$ (see Methods and main text for further details). **b**, Examples of the fluctuating dynamics of the readout activity $y(t)$ following Eq. (7). The decision is taken when the readout activity crosses for the first time (i.e., the reaction time) one of the two threshold values $\pm\theta$ (dashed lines). The example pairs are ‘BA’ (purple) and ‘AD’ (blue) with symbolic distance $SD = +1$ and -3 , respectively. For ‘BA’ two example trials are shown corresponding to both a correct (choose right) and a wrong (choose left) response. Top, probability densities (p.d.f.) of reaction times for the two example pairs. Shaded areas, deciles of the p.d.f. of $y(t)$. Right, asymptotic Gaussian densities of $y(t)$ expected for the two example symbolic distances. **c**, Expected accuracy $\alpha(SD)$ from Eq. (8) of the responses at varying symbolic distance and noise level σ_E . **e**, Accuracy per item from (c) averaged across all item pairs of the test set. **f**, Mean reaction time $RT(SD)$ across symbolic distances and endogenous noise, setting the relaxation time scale τ to have $RT|_{|SD|=1} = 450$ ms.

285 symbolic distance effect clearly emerges (Fig. 5c). Indeed, the accuracy decreases with task difficulty (smaller
 286 $|SD|$) and size σ_E of the endogenous noise. The serial position effect is also recovered (Fig. 5d), such that the
 287 terminal items in the sequence are associated with the highest accuracies. Despite such similarities, a more
 288 careful inspection allows us to find a significant difference between the case of sensory and endogenous noise.
 289 Indeed, performances on terminal items are more affected by σ_E rather than to σ_S . An increase in sensory noise
 290 σ_S (Fig. 3d) leads to a more pronounced U-shaped pattern in performance, while the performance of terminal
 291 items remains relatively stable. Conversely, Fig. 5d shows a general decline in performance at higher levels of
 292 endogenous noise σ_E , for both central and terminal items. Endogenous noise affects the network activity, while
 293 sensory noise directly influences the distributions of the item projections onto the GML. Consequently, central
 294 items are more susceptible to this effect than terminal ones. Increasing sensory noise amplifies the overlap of
 295 central distributions, whereas the impact on terminal items is mitigated by the expansion of their tail distributions,
 296 which aids in distinguishing their rank position.

297 The reaction time RT is the other behavioral output we can workout analytically from the stochastic dynamics
 298 (7) of the readout. In this theoretical framework, RT is the ‘first-passage time’ of the readout activity through the

299 threshold θ . It is a stochastic variable whose mean results to be [51]

$$RT(SD) = \tau \frac{\theta}{SD} \tanh \frac{\theta SD}{\sigma_E^2}. \quad (9)$$

300 As shown in Fig. 5e, the mean response time reduces with the ease of the decision to take, i.e., with the symbolic
 301 distance between the pairs of presented items. This serial position effect is another hallmark of the TI task
 302 [31, 53, 27, 40], according to the well-known speed and accuracy trade-off in decision making [52].

303 In the presence of sensory noise or for specific task protocols, learned GML can lead to readouts y differing
 304 from the symbolic distance SD (Figs. 3e, 4a and d). The formalism developed here remains true in this scenario
 305 as well, provided that the dependency on SD in Eqs. (8) and (9) is replaced by y . This establishes a direct link
 306 between behavior and the GML-based readout of the RNN activity. Indeed, by making use of Eqs. (8) and (9), we
 307 can derive the expression $RT(y) = [2\alpha(y) - 1]\tau\theta/y$, eventually leading to

$$y = \frac{2\alpha - 1}{RT} \tau\theta. \quad (10)$$

308 As both the accuracy α and the reaction time RT are experimentally accessible, this expression allows to infer the
 309 neuronal readout y up to an unknown constant factor $\tau\theta$. Interestingly, this factor is irrelevant if we are interested
 310 in following the relative changes of y across time in experiments with continuous learning, as in the TI task.

311 2.6 Optimal balance between different sources of noise

312 As sensory and endogenous noise differently affect the behavioral performance of the RNN, we further investigate
 313 this aspect in a more realistic scenario. We expose the same linear RNN to a continuous stream of trials where
 314 the usual item representations incorporate the sensory noise introduced in Sect. 2.3 (Fig. 6a). In this *in silico*
 315 experiment, the network state at the beginning of each trial is no more set to 0, as is the case in cortical networks.
 316 The vector of the readout weights $\langle \zeta \rangle$ is learned resorting to the pseudoinverse of the activity matrix aiming at
 317 reproducing the correct choice in the trials with item pairs from the learning set ($y = SD = \pm 1$, see Methods).

318 All these additional sources of uncertainty do not affect the capability of the network to encode the serial
 319 order of the items. Indeed, by stimulating the trained network with each item presented alone, the readout activity
 320 returns a separate distribution of values. According to the expectation such values correspond to the projection
 321 of the network activity onto our GML, where the items are sorted based on their relative rank (Fig. 6b).

322 However, inspecting different combinations of noise levels, it is apparent that only a tight balance between
 323 them allows to have the simultaneous occurrence of the mentioned behavioral effects (dark gray band in Fig. 6c).
 324 In this particular region, when considering an ensemble of 50 randomly selected RNNs, a significant number of
 325 networks exhibit i) an increasing accuracy $\alpha(SD) < \alpha(SD + 1)$ (SDE), ii) a decreasing reaction time with the
 326 symbolic distance $RT(SD) > RT(SD + 1)$ (SDE), and iii) a higher average accuracy for the first and last items
 327 with respect to the central ones (SPE). This analysis is performed by changing both sensory and endogenous
 328 noise levels, here denoted by (σ'_S, σ'_E) . These parameters represent the effect of noise directly on the activity
 329 of the network units and they are tightly correlated with the size of noise fluctuations (σ_S, σ_E) measured along
 330 the GML (see Methods). The existence of a 'sweet' spot for the balance between sensory and endogenous
 331 noise, is even more strikingly represented by the narrow peak in the rate of occurrence of all effects along the
 332 line $\sigma'_S = \sigma'_E$ (Fig. 6d). Such balance clearly emerges from the competition of a two-fold role of the noise. A
 333 destructive role, occurring when it is so large to disrupt the capability of the RNN to produce the correct response,
 334 and a constructive one, as noise is a needed ingredient to have both the symbolic distance and serial position
 335 effects (SDE and SPE, respectively).

336 Although along the narrow band evidenced in Fig. 6c the behavioral effects are similarly reproduced (Fig. 6e),
 337 only when both sensory and endogenous noise have a comparable size (e.g., purple circle, $\sigma'_S = 0.2$ and $\sigma'_E =$
 338 0.4) the RNN has the highest rate of responses (i.e., the fraction of trials in which a decision is taken).

339 2.7 Impact of sequence length and size of the training set

340 Using the above RNN with balanced noise as an *in silico* experiment, we now investigate the impact on some
 341 relevant parameters of the TI task. This is to gain further insights and make predictions about how learning of
 342 serial ordering can be experimentally modulated.

Figure 6: **Behavioral effects in the TI task are reproduced in RNN with noise.** **a**, The same linear RNN as in Fig. 5a receiving a continuous stream of randomized trials of the TI task incorporating simultaneously both the sensory (σ'_S) and the endogenous (σ'_E) noise. The network is trained on the item pairs of the learning set ($|\text{SD}| = 1$) computing the readout weights $\langle \zeta |$ from the pseudoinverse of the network activity assuming a +1 (−1) response when the highest-rank item is on the right (left). When the readout activity crosses for the first time a threshold level ($|y(t)| \geq \theta = 0.5$) the RNN takes a decision. If $y(t)$ does not cross such threshold within 1.5 s from the onset of the item pairs, the trial is not taken into account in the computation of the performances. **b**, Distribution of the post-learning readout activity when only one item is presented per time estimated by presenting a single item per trial for 30 trials each. **c**, Frequency of network realizations (gray shading) capable of reproducing all the behavioral effects expected for the TI task, by varying the size of both the sources of noise (σ'_S and σ'_E). An RNN reproduces such an effect if simultaneously displays i) an accuracy and a reaction time increasing with $|\text{SD}|$ (SDE_{Acc} and SDE_{RT} , respectively) and ii) if the mean accuracy of terminal items is greater than the central ones (SPE). Contours represent the response rate, i.e., the fraction of trials with RNN taking a decision. **d**, Frequency of the behavioral effects (averaged over 50 independent RNN realizations) for varying balanced levels of noise ($\sigma'_S = \sigma'_E$). **e**, Behavioral effects (averaged over 50 RNNs) co-occurring in different noise regimes pointed out in (c) by colored circles: strongly endogenous (red), balanced (purple) and strongly sensory (cyan) noise. The balanced noise case is the one with the highest frequency of responses. Reaction times are normalized to 1 for $|\text{SD}| = 1$.

343 Firstly we focus on the size of the training set (Fig. 7a). For a small number of learning trials, noise is too
 344 high to reach significant performances, limiting the capability to reliably estimate the proper vector of readout
 345 weights. This leads to indistinguishable projections of the network activity onto the GML with almost equally low
 346 performances and long reaction times (lighter curves). Increasing the number of learning trials, all the behavioral
 347 effects are recovered. Interestingly, we found the accuracy displays a change of concavity in the performances
 348 and a flattening in the SPE for mid-rank items, which can be explained by the sigmoidal dependence highlighted
 349 in Eq. (8).

350 By increasing the number of items to be sorted in the TI task, a strong modulation of the psychometric curves
 351 can be also observed (Fig. 7b). SDE displays a change of concavity both in the reaction times and in the accuracy
 352 leading to more rapid changes for larger symbolic distances. Another interesting effect is the equalization of the
 353 middle-rank representations as soon as the lowest possible accuracy of 0.5 is approached: a barrier limiting the
 354 maximum number of items that can be sorted.

Figure 7: **TI task in RNN with varying number of training trials and items to sort.** **a.** Behavioral effects: SDE for the accuracy and the reaction time and SPE from left to right, respectively. Number of learning trials range from 4 to 20. Network as in Fig. 6 with $\sigma'_S = 0.2$, $\sigma'_E = 0.4$. Accuracy and reaction times are averaged across 50 random realizations of the RNN. **b.** Behavioral effects as in (a) for increasing numbers of items in the sequence to sort. Items number range from 6 to 20.

2.8 Learning the GML in RNN taking motor decisions

So far we studied how the GML $\langle \zeta |$ is learned assuming that the only plastic synapses were those between the network units x_i and the readout y . Here we investigate a more realistic framework, where the cerebral network involved in a TI task is represented by an RNN encoding the ‘motor’ output by confining its activity $|x\rangle$ within a low-dimensional latent space [54]. Such choice follows from the experimental evidence that the premotor cortex (PMC) of monkeys contributes to the motor decision in a TI task with neuronal activity modulated by the symbolic distance between item pairs [40].

To this purpose, in addition to the sensory input $g_S |S_R - S_L\rangle$, the RNN introduced in Fig. 6 receives also the motor-related input $g_M |\mu\rangle$ (Fig. 8a) (see Methods). As shown later, this additional input determines the axis along which the network activity is forced to unfold as the decision to move is taken. With this, we aim at roughly modeling motor plans known to be encoded in PMC. The relationship between g_S and g_M modulates the relative strength of the sensory and motor input to the network. As in previous network configurations, the learning phase involves only the set of pairs $\{S_j, S_k\}$ with symbolic distance $|\text{SD}| = |r_j - r_k| = 1$ (Fig. 2a), and we impose $y = +1$ (-1) when the item to reach is on the right (left). In this phase the mental line $\langle \zeta |$ is computed resorting to the pseudo-inverse of the RNN activity in the absence of feedback (i.e., without re-injecting $y = \langle \zeta | x \rangle$ as a factor of $|\mu\rangle$, see Methods).

In simulation we tested the response of the RNN with feedback to all possible item pairs, finding that it successfully solved the task. Indeed, by performing a principal component analysis (PCA) on the network states, the neural trajectories in the latent plane (PC_1, y) clearly cluster according to the symbolic distance of the presented pairs (Fig. 8b-bottom). The trajectories slopes are higher for higher SD, reflecting a change in the driving force proportional to task difficulty. Besides, the asymptotic value of the readout $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} y(t) = y_\infty$ returns the symbolic distance $\text{SD} = r_k - r_j$.

For our linear RNN, this can be analytically proven as the asymptotic activity is $|x_\infty\rangle \equiv \lim_{t \gg \tau} |x(t)\rangle = |\tilde{S}_R - \tilde{S}_L\rangle + y_\infty |\tilde{\mu}\rangle$. Here $|\tilde{S}_k\rangle$ and $|\tilde{\mu}\rangle$ are the inner representations of the presented items and of the motor plan, respectively, transformed by the activity reverberation in the network (see Methods). As a result, the GML has to be

$$\langle \zeta | \equiv \sum_{k=1}^M (r_k + \varphi) \langle \tilde{S}_k | + \langle \gamma |, \quad (11)$$

holding for any real φ and row vector $\langle \gamma |$ orthogonal to the subspace where the item representations $\langle \tilde{S}_k |$ and

Figure 8: **RNNs with feedback learn the GML reducing the dimensionality of the latent space.** **a**, RNN as in Fig. 5 with the additional input mediated by the weights $|\mu\rangle$ with strength g_M eventually modulated by the feedback (solid arrow) provided by the readout y . During the learning phase, only pairs of items with unitary symbolic distance are presented (as in Fig. 3a). The correct action (i.e., move right (left) to reach the winning item) is represented by the input $|+\mu\rangle$ ($|-\mu\rangle$) (dotted arrow). **b**, Neural trajectories of the RNN during the test phase (as in Fig. 3a). The learned GML $\langle\zeta|$ results from the pseudo-inverse performed on the neural activity of the learning. Principal component analysis (PCA) is performed on the neural activity of the whole test phase. Trajectories are shown in the planar subspace determined by the projection of the network activity on $\langle\zeta|$ and the first PC (bottom), and in the plane of the first and second PCs (top). Colors code for the symbolic distance between the items of the presented pair $\{S_L, S_R\}$. Here, the RNN has $N = 100$, $|x(0)\rangle = 0$, $g = 0.1$, $g_S = 0.01$ and $g_M = 0.02$ (see Methods for other parameters and task details). **c**, Variance explained by the first principal component PC_1 , varying the feedback strength g_M for an RNN with the same parameters as in (b). Inset, variance explained by first 15 PCs for the RNN with $g_M = 0.01$. **d**, Mean correlation $1/N \sum_{i=1}^N \langle y x_i \rangle$ averaged across trials with pairs having the same absolute symbolic distance: $|\text{SD}| = |r_R - r_L|$. Mean correlations *versus* $|\text{SD}|$ are shown for networks with varying feedback strength g_M . Other parameters: $g = 0.05$ and $g_S = 0.01$.

382 motor plan $\langle\tilde{\mu}|$ live. This expression is equivalent to the GML derived in Eq. (4), confirming it is a general solution
 383 holding also for RNN with feedback. Note that the found $\langle\zeta|$ does not depend on the motor plan. Thus, although
 384 both the sensory and the motor engrams coexist in the network, they do not interfere.

385 In Fig. 8b-top it is interesting to note that a richer structure of neural trajectories emerges in the plane of the
 386 first two principal components (PC_1, PC_2). Trials with the same symbolic distance SD now split, unfolding the
 387 information about the items in the presented pairs. This is a direct consequence of the fact that representations
 388 of item pairs occupy an M -dimensional subspace (Fig. 1d), and this information persists in the asymptotic state
 389 of the network in Eq. (17). Recurrent activity transforms these internal representations aligning the network state
 390 along the axis $|\tilde{\mu}\rangle$, which in turn is the average $|x_\infty\rangle$ across trials. For this reason, the stronger is the feedback g_M ,
 391 the larger is the variance explained by PC_1 (Fig. 8c). Not only, as in the above expression for $|x_\infty\rangle$ (i.e., Eq. (17)
 392 in Methods) the contribution of the motor component is also proportional to the symbolic distance $\text{SD} = y_\infty$,
 393 also the activity level of the network units are expected to grow according to SD. Such correlation is apparent in
 394 Fig. 8b-bottom for the example network, and we found it to be weakened by the increase of the feedback strength
 395 g_M (Fig. 8d). This is due to the sigmoidal activation $\Phi(h)$ limiting the activity x_i to be in the range $[-1, +1]$.

396 To summarize, networks with feedback are capable of encoding simultaneously both motor-related activity and
 397 the same geometric mental line found in more simplistic conditions. The dimensionality of the latent state-space
 398 of the network is compressed according to the strength g_M of the learned feedback. This can limit the degree of
 399 correlation between the activity of the network units and the symbolic distance of presented pairs. Remarkably, a
 400 similar SD-dependent modulation of the motor-selective activity was found in PMC neurons of monkeys performing a
 401 TI task [40].

3 Discussion

The brain encodes task relevant information into complex dynamical patterns of neuronal activity, requiring a high-dimensional state space to be embedded [9, 55]. These high-dimensional representations have the great advantage of being linearly separable, as random projections of correlated representations tend to be orthogonal in the target high-dimensional neural space, according to the ‘efficient coding hypothesis’ [56, 57]. Linearly separable representations can be indeed categorized *via* relatively simple learning rules eventually leading to a dimensional reduction of the output-potent space [58]. Remarkably, such low-dimensional latent spaces where correlated neural activity is constrained to wander, are pervasively found in associative cortices of many species suggesting it as a successful computational strategy preserved across evolution [59, 60, 8].

Here we widen the realm of cognitive functions by exploiting such “expansion-compression” computational paradigm to the representations of stimuli and behavioral output in neuronal networks. We indeed prove that the task of arbitrarily ranking a set of M abstract items can be always performed by looking at the projections of their inner representations onto a suited low-dimensional subspace. Centroids of these projections can be arbitrarily mapped on any monotonic function of the ranks assigned to the items. The subspace where item ranks are encoded works as a “geometrical mental line” (GML), given by a suited linear combination of the item representations. In a network composed by N neurons, the GML is not unique as all the $N - M$ dimensions of the residual state space are unconstrained, leading to an infinite set of solutions. As a result, other network resources can in principle be used simultaneously to encode additional information and/or to perform complementary computations. The existence of a GML thus implies that the dimensionality of the representational space reduces from M to one as a byproduct of the nonlinear dynamics naturally occurring into a recurrent neuronal network, compressing the information about the ranks into a scalar magnitude. The resulting one-dimensional manifold straightforwardly informs about the motor decision (output) to take, which in turn we have shown to be modulated by task difficulty (i.e., different symbolic distances).

Thanks to the fact that our model is based on the linear combination of representations, the GML is highly flexible [9, 61, 62] and different directions can be read out for different arbitrary orders of the same set of items (Figure 2). This supports the idea that in serial reasoning two different representations must be learned [3]: the item representations, which are stored in a suited neural subspace, and the ordinal information, which depends on the readouts shaped by learning constrained by the task to perform.

Intriguingly, the geometrical mental line successfully faces task sets never seen during the learning phase. This capability to generalize is a hallmark of serial reasoning needed to solve the transitive inference task. The formulation of a geometrical solution of a task is the backbone of many cognitive models of serial reasoning [10, 62, 63, 64]. The idea is that in cognitive processes, it is important to consider both the content and the geometrical structure of the neural activity, which fixes the relationships between the relevant variables of the task. In the specific case of transitive inference, the geometric framework underlying the task is widely believed to be a linear workspace [12, 65, 66, 67, 68]. The GML we derived represents this one-dimensional manifold allowing to solve the TI task. Taking into account the intrinsic uncertainty of item representations (sensory noise) and the intrinsic stochasticity of the neuronal activity (endogenous noise), simulated recurrent neural networks (RNNs) reproduced all the behavioral effects observed in experiments: i) the symbolic distance effect, both in performances and reaction times, and ii) the serial position effect. These results can be explained in terms of a varying signal-to-noise ratio for different couples of items. Adding noise to the item representations leads RNNs to visit a state subspace with a dimensionality higher than the length M of the item list. Consequently, the learned GML moves away from being entirely contained in the M -dimensional space of the items as prescribed by Eq. (3). A rotation occurs (Fig. 3e) without affecting the effectiveness of the GML in coding the serial order of the items. Such a widening of dimensionality can be countered by encoding simultaneously other task-relevant information like the motor plan of behavioral responses (Fig. 8). From this we expect that the expansion and compression of the latent state-space visited by cortical networks probed in *in vivo* [38, 29, 40], is differently expressed during the execution of the TI task.

Further investigating the same RNN, some predictions arose about different task settings, e.g., changing the number of training trials or changing the number M of items in the learned sequence. This offers an interesting perspective to understand the predictive power of our theoretical framework looking at direct comparisons with behavioral data from experiments [69]. Focusing on the specific case of item sequences with increasing lengths, we expect to see a change in the concavity of the accuracy in the SDE (Fig. 7b) together with a flattening of the performances for central items in the SPE. This kind of model predictions can inform about the limitations of the

455 network in the capability to store serial-order information. These limitations are usually worked around in animal
456 experiments resorting to the so-called ‘linking chain paradigm’ [37, 70]. It would be then interesting to investigate
457 this learning paradigm within our theoretical framework.

458 Furthermore, we proved that the GML can be naturally embedded into an RNN designed to make motor
459 decisions. In this case, a one-dimensional manifold naturally emerges in the latent space visited by network
460 activity, which is aligned to the motor plan encoding the decision to take. Such dynamical organization of the
461 network dynamics accounts for the expected modulation of single-unit activity observed in the premotor cortex
462 (PMC) of monkeys: the larger the SD (higher response value in the RNN, as predicted by the theoretical GML),
463 the larger the number of units in the RNN exceeding a given activity threshold.

464 Starting from this evidence we speculate that PMC might be an ideal candidate to implement the GML solution
465 when the transitive inference task is learned and successfully performed. We can also speculate that this mental
466 line representation might play a role well before movement onset, as it has been shown that in the delay period
467 following the presentation of the item pairs, the decision is already taken and the symbolic distance is no more
468 relevant [71].

469 Notably, we also found that in addition to the symbolic distance, the GML allows our network models to provide
470 as a read out the joint rank (i.e., the rank sum) of item pairs. This happens if the item representations are summed
471 ($|S_R + S_L|$) instead of being subtracted ($|S_R - S_L|$). Interestingly, in the posterior parietal cortex of non-human
472 primates neuronal activity was found to correlate with the joint rank despite the fact that it was not a relevant
473 information to solve the TI task [29]. According to this evidence, a reasonable hypothesis to test is that different
474 sensory pathways might coexist implementing the sum and the difference of item representations presented in
475 pair. In this way, cortical networks would be spontaneously ready to respond according to both the symbolic
476 distance and the joint rank, a kind of primitive algebraic competence.

477 Regarding the linear combination of item representations determining the GML $\langle \zeta |$ in Eq. (3), it is important
478 to remark that the coefficients (i.e., the projection values) of such combination are given by the item ranks r_k .
479 This is due to the fact that the TI task is learned on trials with item pairs with $|SD| = 1$. However, depending on
480 the training procedure adopted in the serial learning task, the response can be shaped as a function $f(r_k)$ of the
481 item ranks, as emphasized in Eq. (3). As shown in Fig. 4, this is the case of the biased TI task we introduced,
482 having reward probabilistically assigned as a function of the mean rank of the presented pairs. Note that, in
483 the experimental literature there are several other possible modifications of the reward schedule that we expect
484 can change the projection values embedded into the GML, without affecting the capability to encode the correct
485 order in the sequence ([39, 27, 72]). Alternatively, also the number of trials composing the learning phase can
486 have a similar impact, as it affects the quality of item representations experienced (Fig. 7a). We explicitly tested
487 such a possibility in modeling the ISR task in which all items have equally corrupted representations ($\beta = 0$)
488 but are not always present in the list to recall. More specifically, in some learning trials items are randomly
489 removed from the list, such that each of them is presented a fraction of times decreasing with their serial position
490 (Supplementary Fig. 1). In this way, items seen fewer times will be represented more weakly in the GML. The
491 larger the difference between the number of trials per item, the stronger the nonlinearity of the rank-readout
492 mapping. Starting from this evidence, we can imagine a scaling of the number of presentations leading to the
493 logarithmic function $f(r_k) = \log(r_k)$, as in the case of an over-training of the low-rank items as hypothesized in
494 the ordering of numerical quantities [73, 74, 75, 76, 32]. In these conditions, the activity projection onto $\langle \zeta |$ (i.e.,
495 the network readout y) are no more equally spaced: the first items have a greater distance along the GML. This
496 might explain some behavioral effects, such as those following the Weber’s principle formalized as Fechner’s law
497 [77, 78], giving rise to the well-known primacy effect possibly observed in various serial learning tasks (e.g., in the
498 simultaneous chain task [79, 15]).

499 Finally, we remark that several models have been proposed to explain how a mental scheme of the items ranks
500 could be learned by humans and animals [31, 32, 80, 81, 82], and what is the role of the reward in this process
501 [83, 69]. An intriguing and open question is then, whether such theoretical frameworks together with the one we
502 presented here, are capable of predicting effects not yet observed sharpening their range of applicability, and thus
503 shedding further light on the brain mechanisms underlying serial thinking.

504 Methods

505 RNN dynamics and its linearization

506 Recurrent neural networks (RNN) are composed of N units ($N = 100$, unless otherwise specified in the main
507 text). The j -th unit has activity state $x_j(t) = \{|x(t)\rangle\}_j$ evolving according to the first-order dynamics

$$\tau \dot{x}_j = \Phi(h_j) - x_j$$

508 for any $j \in [1, N] \subset \mathbb{Z}$. The decay time constant $\tau = 0.1s$ and the activation function $\Phi(h_j) \equiv \tanh(h_j)$ is the
509 same for all units. These dynamical systems serve as effective models of cortical networks, as they can be viewed
510 as networks of local cell assemblies, which are the units composing the RNN. Under mean-field approximation,
511 each of these assemblies, composed of excitatory (glutamatergic) and inhibitory (GABAergic) neurons, can be
512 described by a similar low-dimensional dynamics of the firing rate $x(t)$ [84, 85, 86, 87, 26]. The synaptic input
513 $h_j = \{|h\rangle\}_j$ is the weighted sum

$$h_j(t) = \sum_{k=1}^N W_{jk} x_k(t) + h_{j,\text{ext}}(t)$$

514 where W_{jk} are the element of the synaptic matrix $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ sampled randomly from a Gaussian distribution
515 with 0 mean and standard deviation g/\sqrt{N} . $h_{j,\text{ext}}(t)$ is the external input received by the unit j . The network
516 dynamics is integrated relying on the first-order Euler-Maruyama method with time step $dt = 0.1\tau$ to take into
517 account the possible sources of noise in the input detailed in the main text and in the following. In matrix form, the
518 above dynamics can be compactly written as

$$\tau |\dot{x}\rangle = |\Phi(h)\rangle - |x\rangle \quad (12)$$

519 with

$$|h\rangle = \mathbf{W} |x\rangle + |h_{\text{ext}}\rangle ,$$

520 where the ‘kets’ $|\cdot\rangle \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 1}$ are column vectors.

521 During the serial ranking tasks discussed in the main text, the presentation of items on the screen is modeled
522 as a modulation of the external input. More specifically, the single k -th item elicits a sensory input $|h_{\text{ext}}\rangle = g_S |S_k\rangle$
523 with strength g_S set to 1 when not specified otherwise. The vector elements $S_{ki} = \{|S_k\rangle\}_i$ are i.i.d. random
524 variables with zero mean and variance $1/N$. The ‘bras’ $\langle S_k| \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N}$ are the row vectors transposed of $|S_k\rangle$, such
525 that in the large-network limit, the inner product is

$$\langle S_j | S_k \rangle \equiv \sum_{n=1}^N S_{jn} S_{kn} \xrightarrow{N \rightarrow \infty} \delta_{jk} . \quad (13)$$

526 When two items are simultaneously presented as in the TI task, the input received by the network is a linear
527 combination of the isolated stimuli: $|h_{\text{ext}}\rangle = g_S (|S_j\rangle - |S_k\rangle) \equiv g_S |S_j - S_k\rangle$. For the sake of simplicity, the item
528 k presented on the left side of the screen has negative strength, while the j -th located on the right contributes
529 as it would be alone. Such a peculiar modeling choice is not critical and can be generalized as shown below
530 (Subsection ‘GML with arbitrary item representations’).

531 When both the spectral radius g of \mathbf{W} and the strength g_S of the sensory input are small ($g, g_S \ll 1$), the
532 dynamics of the RNN can be linearized. Indeed, under these conditions assuming a sensory and endogenous
533 noise of the same order of magnitude (see below), the synaptic input h_j is expected to be of the same order.
534 Hence, the activation function can be approximated as $\Phi(h_j) \simeq \Phi(0) + h_j \Phi'(0) = h_j$, and Eq. (12) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \tau |\dot{x}\rangle &= |h\rangle - |x\rangle \\ &= -(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W}) |x\rangle + |h_{\text{ext}}\rangle . \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

535 As above, at rest $|h_{\text{ext}}\rangle = |0\rangle$, while when the pair of items j and k appears to the right and to the left of the
536 screen, respectively, $|h_{\text{ext}}\rangle = g_S |S_R - S_L\rangle$ with $S_R = S_j$ and $S_L = S_k$. All the RNNs studied in this work operate
537 within the linear regime and as such follow the dynamics (14).

538 Linear RNN and motor decision

539 In the linear RNN introduced in Sect. 2.5, we impose that the response unfolds along an independent 1-dimensional
 540 manifold encoding the motor plan. To this purpose an additional motor-related input $g_M |\mu\rangle$ is added to $|h_{\text{ext}}\rangle$ fur-
 541 ther modulated by the expected response $y'(t)$ leading to the linear dynamics

$$\tau |\dot{x}\rangle = -(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W}) |x\rangle + g_S |S_R - S_L\rangle + y' g_M |\mu\rangle . \quad (15)$$

542 Here g_S and g_M modulate the strength of the sensory and motor-related inputs, respectively. As the item repre-
 543 sentations $|S_k\rangle$, the ‘motor’ axis $|\mu\rangle$ is extracted randomly making all these engrams orthogonal (i.e., $\langle S_k | \mu \rangle = 0$
 544 for any item k) in the limit of infinitely large networks ($N \rightarrow \infty$).

545 In the learning phase involving only the set of pairs $\{S_j, S_k\}$ with unitary symbolic distance, i.e., $|\text{SD}| =$
 546 $|r_j - r_k| = 1$ (see Fig. 2a), the expected response is $y' = +1$ (-1) when the item to reach is on the right (left).
 547 As in the standard reservoir computing framework [88], if the GML $\langle \zeta |$ solving the task $y' = \langle \zeta | x \rangle$ exists, it results
 548 from a linear regression of the activity leading to a new synaptic matrix

$$\mathbf{W} \rightarrow \mathbf{W} + g_M |\mu\rangle \langle \zeta | , \quad (16)$$

549 where the rank-1 matrix $g_M |\mu\rangle \langle \zeta |$ represents the changes induced by learning.

550 In simulations, we computed the mental line $\langle \zeta |$ during the learning phase, resorting to the pseudo-inverse
 551 of the neural activity of the RNN without feedback (i.e., without re-injecting $\langle \zeta | x \rangle$ as the factor of $|\mu\rangle$). We then
 552 updated the synaptic matrix according to Eq. (16), eventually testing the response of the RNN with feedback to
 553 all possible item pairs. In this testing phase only the sensory input $g_S |S_R - S_L\rangle$ is provided, as the motor plan
 554 spontaneously emerged from the recurrent activity of the linear RNN.

555 From Eq. (15) the asymptotic state of the network following the presentation of a pair of items can be carried
 556 out by imposing $|\dot{x}\rangle = 0$, which results to be

$$\begin{aligned} |x_\infty\rangle &\equiv \lim_{t \gg \tau} |x(t)\rangle = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W})^{-1} \{g_S |S_R - S_L\rangle + y_\infty g_M |\mu\rangle\} \\ &\equiv |\tilde{S}_R - \tilde{S}_L\rangle + y_\infty |\tilde{\mu}\rangle . \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

557 Here $|\tilde{S}_k\rangle$ and $|\tilde{\mu}\rangle$ are the inner representations of the presented items and of the motor plan, respectively,
 558 transformed by the activity reverberation in the network.

559 Even in this general case it is easy to prove that the geometric mental line $\langle \zeta |$ solving the TI task is given by a
 560 linear combination of row vectors $\langle \tilde{S}_k | \equiv g_S^{-1} \langle S_k | (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W})$. Indeed, for such vectors, the following relationships
 561 hold: i) $\langle \tilde{S}_j | \tilde{S}_k \rangle = \delta_{jk}$ and ii) $\langle \tilde{S}_k | \tilde{\mu} \rangle = 0$. With that, by imposing $\langle \zeta | x_\infty \rangle = r_R - r_L$ for all the item pairs with
 562 $|\text{SD}| = 1$, an infinite set of geometric mental lines exist and they are

$$\langle \zeta | = \sum_{k=1}^M (r_k + \varphi) \langle \tilde{S}_k | + \langle \gamma | , \quad (18)$$

563 i.e., Eq. (11) reported in the main text. Note that by setting $\mathbf{W} = 0$ and $g_S = 1$ the simple linear-Perceptron
 564 configuration introduced in the main text is recovered, eventually making the above expression equivalent to
 565 Eq. (3).

566 From Eq. (15) we can work out the evolution in time of the readout $y(t)$ and the projection $z(t) \equiv \langle \mu | x \rangle$
 567 expected to faithfully represent the loading of the PC_1 . Indeed applying to both hand sides of such equation the
 568 ‘bra’ $\langle \mu |$ and $\langle \zeta |$ we obtain the following analytical approximations

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{y} &= -(1 - g_M \langle \zeta | \mu \rangle) y + r_R - r_L , \\ \dot{z} &= -z + g_M y , \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

569 where we assumed that both $\langle \zeta | \mathbf{W} | x \rangle$ and $\langle \mu | \mathbf{W} | x \rangle$ are approximately equal to 0 as we verified numerically in
 570 simulation. From this expression, it can be noted that the network activity starting from $|x\rangle = 0$ initially unfolds
 571 being driven exclusively by the information $|S_k - S_j\rangle$. As a result, the speed of changes in the readout y are given
 572 by the symbolic distance $r_R - r_L$. This explains why the slope of the trajectories in Fig. 8b are steeper for item
 573 pairs with larger rank difference. Afterward, the contribution from the activity $z(t)$ along $|\mu\rangle$ starts to play a role
 574 being modulated by a $y(t)$, as it is apparent from Fig. 8b-bottom looking at the slopes of the trajectories around
 575 $\text{PC}_1 = 0$. We finally remark that the asymptotic value of $z_\infty = \lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} z(t)$ returns to be fully correlated with the
 576 projection of the network activity onto the GML: $z_\infty = g_M y_\infty = g_M (r_R - r_L)$.

577 Linear RNN with sensory and endogenous noise

578 In Sect. 2.5, the dynamics (14) of the above linear RNN incorporates units receiving a stochastic input. This is
 579 done by adding to the input $|h\rangle$ an endogenous noise $|\xi^{(T)}\rangle$ uncorrelated in time whose elements $\xi_k^{(T)}(t)$ are i.i.d.
 580 random variables extracted from a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and an arbitrary variance $\sigma_T'^2/dt$. Here,
 581 the endogenous noise aims at modeling the stochasticity expressed by biological networks of neurons working in
 582 a condition of balanced excitation and inhibition [25, 89]. Indeed, in our theoretical framework, each unit of the
 583 RNN represents a local cell assembly composed of a finite number K of neurons. For this reason the collective
 584 dynamics of a unit (i.e., the population firing rate $x_k(t)$) is a stochastic variable with fluctuation size proportional
 585 to $1/\sqrt{K}$ [86, 26, 90].

586 Sensory input in this network configuration is given by the superposition of the contributions due to the pre-
 587 sented items ($|h_{ext}\rangle = g_S |S_R - S_L\rangle$) eventually leading to the linearized dynamics

$$\tau \dot{x} = -(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W}) |x\rangle + g_S |S_R - S_L\rangle + \mathbf{W} |\xi^{(T)}\rangle . \quad (20)$$

588 In this framework, the readout weights $\langle \zeta |$ given by Eq. (3) make the network capable of solving on average the TI
 589 task provided that they are rescaled by $1/g_S$ (i.e, $\langle \zeta | = 1/g_S \sum_{k=1}^M r_k \langle S_k |$). Indeed, applying to both hand sides
 590 of Eq. (20) the rescaled GML we obtain the stochastic dynamics

$$\tau \dot{y} = -y + g_S \langle \zeta | S_R - S_L \rangle + \langle \zeta | \mathbf{W} \xi^{(T)} \rangle ,$$

591 where we neglected the $\mathcal{O}(g)$ terms approximating $\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W} \simeq \mathbf{I}$. Here $\langle \zeta | \mathbf{W} \xi^{(T)} \rangle$ results to be a Gaussian random
 592 variable with zero mean and variance $\sigma_E^2/dt \equiv (\sigma_T' g/g_S)^2 \sum_{k=1}^M r_k^2/dt$ which for $r_k = k$ gives

$$\sigma_E^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_T' g}{g_S} \right)^2 \frac{M(1+M)(1+2M)}{6} . \quad (21)$$

593 This because the vector and matrix elements S_{ki} , W_{ij} and $\xi_j^{(T)}$ are i.i.d. random Gaussian variables with
 594 zero mean and variance $1/N$, g^2/N and $\sigma_T'^2/dt$, respectively. Considering that for the chosen readout weights
 595 $g_S \langle \zeta | S_R - S_L \rangle = r_R - r_L$, the stochastic dynamics of the readout $y(t)$ eventually reduces to Eq. (7) in Sect. 7:

$$\tau dy = (-y + r_R - r_L) dt + \sigma_E dW ,$$

596 where $y(t)$ is driven by a Gaussian white noise $dW(t)$ with zero mean and covariance $\mathbb{E}[dW(t)dW(t')] = \delta(t -$
 597 $t')dt$.

598 In addition to endogenous noise, the model incorporates sensory noise to account for the variability in en-
 599 coding visual stimuli across trials. The actual contribution of the presented pair of items in a generic trial n is
 600 given by: $|h_{ext}\rangle = |S_k + \xi_n^{(R)}\rangle - |S_j + \xi_n^{(L)}\rangle$, where $|\xi_n^{(L,R)}\rangle$ is a vector of i.i.d. Gaussian values with zero mean
 601 and standard deviation σ_S' . This leads to a random contribution to the item direction $|S_k\rangle$ with a variance of
 602 $\mathbb{V}[\langle S_k | \xi_n^{(R,L)} \rangle] = \sigma_S'^2$, and for the projection along the GML $\mathbb{V}[\langle \zeta | \xi_n^{(R,L)} \rangle] = \sigma_S'^2/g_S^2 \sum_{k=1}^M r_k^2 = \sigma_S^2$. Given $r_k = k$,
 603 the following relationship holds

$$\sigma_S^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_S'}{g_S} \right)^2 \frac{M(1+M)(1+2M)}{6} .$$

604 In order to preserve the linear approximation of the dynamics, the effective intensity of sensory contribution
 605 $\mathbb{V}[g_S |h_{ext}\rangle]$ is fixed rescaling g_S by a factor $1/(1 + \sigma_S')$. Finally, the stochastic dynamics of the readout $y(t)$,
 606 considering the two noise sources, is updated as follows

$$\tau dy = \left(-y + r_R - r_L + \sqrt{2}\sigma_S \Gamma_n \right) dt + \sigma_E dW$$

607 where Γ_n is an independent random Gaussian variable with zero mean and unit variance.

608 Linear RNN parameters and task design

609 Regarding the simulated linear RNN, they have random connectivity with spectral radius $g = 0.05$ and strength of
 610 sensory input $g_S = 0.2g$. Each item is schematized by injecting a square-wave current lasting $1.5s$, smoothed by

611 a Gaussian-weighted moving average filter (0.15 s bandwidth) and followed by a relaxation time of 3s. The state
 612 history associated with the items pairs with adjacent rank ($|SD| = 1$) randomly presented 20 times each, is used
 613 to estimate the vector of readout weights through the pseudo-inverse approach, eventually determining a motor
 614 response when the activity of the readout unit y crosses a threshold value of 0.5. The behavior of the network
 615 for other threshold values at various feedback strengths is shown in Supplementary Fig. 2. The accuracy of the
 616 responses is tested across the whole set of possible item pairs (i.e., the testing set) presented for 20 times.

617 The task visual stimuli are simulated by stimulating groups of nodes with a square wave current, positive when
 618 the stimulus is placed on the right side of the screen, negative when it is placed on the left. As previously shown,
 619 two different sources of noise are considered: sensory (σ'_S) and endogenous noise (σ'_E). The interplay between
 620 the two sources in the operation of the recurrent neural network is illustrated in Fig. 6.

621 The network is trained on couples of nearest-neighbor symbols, computing the linear readout such that the
 622 state of the system gives +1 when the target item is on the right and -1 when it is on the left. The resulting output
 623 is an accumulation process that triggers a choice once a threshold of 0.5 is overcome. If the signal does not reach
 624 the threshold within the 1.5 s of the square wave stimulation the trial is not taken into account in the performance
 625 computation.

626 GML with arbitrary item representations

627 For the sake of simplicity in the main text, we assumed that item representations on one side of the screen (left
 628 or right) are associated with opposite network states, such that $\langle S_{kL}|S_{kR}\rangle = -1$ for any $k \in [1, M]$. Here we
 629 prove that even when this assumption is relaxed, the GML is still a linear combination of the decoding weights
 630 discriminating both the presence and the position of the k -th item on the screen, as in Eq. (3). To this purpose
 631 let's consider the general case of correlated representations for the same item presented in different positions
 632 ($\langle S_{k\alpha}|S_{j\beta}\rangle = 0$, $\langle S_{k\alpha}|S_{k\beta}\rangle \neq 0$ for any $k \neq j$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \{L, R\}$). This choice is justified by the efficient
 633 coding hypothesis such that sensory information is orthogonalized via random projects onto a high-dimensional
 634 representational space [56, 57]. However, it is reasonable to expect that some degree ρ_k of correlation exists
 635 between the representations of the same item appearing in different positions of the screen: $\langle S_{k,L}|S_{k,R}\rangle = \rho_k$. In
 636 this case, the GML solving the TI task from the learning phase must solve the following set of $2(M - 1)$ equations

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \zeta | S_{k+1,R} + S_{k,L} \rangle &= +1 \\ \langle \zeta | S_{k,R} + S_{k+1,L} \rangle &= -1 \end{aligned}$$

637 for any $k \in [1, M - 1]$.

638 Making also, in this case, the ansatz $\langle \zeta | = \sum_{\alpha \in \{L,R\}} \sum_{k=1}^M a_{k\alpha} \langle S_{k\alpha} |$, the above set of equations allows to
 639 work out the coefficients $a_{k\alpha}$ for the decision to choose the highest item on the right

$$\begin{aligned} +1 &= a_{k+1,L} \langle S_{k+1,L} | S_{k+1,R} \rangle + a_{k+1,R} \langle S_{k+1,R} | S_{k+1,R} \rangle + a_{kR} \langle S_{kR} | S_{kL} \rangle + a_{kL} \langle S_{kL} | S_{kL} \rangle \\ &= (a_{k+1,R} + a_{k+1,L} \rho_{k+1}) + (a_{kL} + a_{kR} \rho_k) , \end{aligned}$$

640 or on the left

$$-1 = (a_{kR} + a_{kL} \rho_k) + (a_{k+1,L} + a_{k+1,R} \rho_{k+1}) .$$

641 Summing these two equations we obtain

$$0 = (a_{kR} + a_{kL}) (1 + \rho_k) + (a_{k+1,R} + a_{k+1,L}) (1 + \rho_{k+1})$$

642 which are always solved if $a_{kL} = -a_{kR}$ for any $k \in [1, M]$. This together with the difference of the previous two
 643 equations leads to have

$$2 = 2a_{kL} (1 - \rho_k) - 2a_{k+1,L} (1 - \rho_{k+1}) ,$$

644 eventually allowing us to write the solution

$$a_{kR} = -a_{kL} = \frac{k}{1 - \rho_k} . \quad (22)$$

645 Given these coefficients, the generalized GML result to be

$$\langle \zeta | = \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{k}{1 - \rho_k} \langle S_{kR} - S_{kL} | . \quad (23)$$

646 Note that in the simplified case discussed in the main text ($\rho_k = -1$) the GML Eq. (3) is recovered as $\langle S_{kL} | =$
647 $-\langle S_{kR} |$.

648 To further prove the generality of our theoretical framework, we finally consider representations of items that
649 are independent but correlated, i.e., $\langle S_k | S_j \rangle \neq 0$ for all $k, j \in [1, M]$. In this scenario, we can isolate the indepen-
650 dent component of each item by using a projector matrix \mathbf{P} to map the item representations S_k to an orthogonal
651 basis. Notably, previous analyses remain valid with the updated representational vectors $|S_k^*\rangle = \mathbf{P} |S_k\rangle$ and the
652 row vectors $\langle S_k^*| = \langle S_k| \mathbf{P}^\top$, ensuring that $\langle S_k^* | S_j^* \rangle = 0$ for all $k \neq j$.

653 GML with arbitrary motor plan

654 In Sect. 2.8, we consider the motor axis as not belonging to the space of item representations, and we identify
655 the GML family that solves the task. However, we can also find a GML solution in the case of non-orthogonality
656 between items and motor representations.

657 Let us consider the more general case in which the inner product $\langle \tilde{S}_k | \tilde{\mu} \rangle = \rho_k$, and assume that a GML
658 solution $\langle \zeta |$ exists and solves the task such that $y_\infty = \langle \zeta | x_\infty \rangle = \text{SD}$. The GML solution $\langle \zeta_0 |$, defined for $\rho_k = 0$
659 and presented in Eq. (18), projects the state as

$$\langle \zeta_0 | x_\infty \rangle = \text{SD} + \text{SD} \langle \zeta_0 | \tilde{\mu} \rangle. \quad (24)$$

660 By isolating the SD, it reads

$$\frac{\langle \zeta_0 | x_\infty \rangle}{1 + \sum_k (r_k + \varphi) \rho_k} = \text{SD} = \langle \zeta | x_\infty \rangle, \quad (25)$$

661 For the sake of simplicity, we have neglected the degeneracy vector $\langle \gamma |$ in the orthogonal space. Therefore, the
662 updated GML is a rescaled version of the solution defined in Eq. (18). In particular, it holds that

$$\langle \zeta | = \frac{\langle \zeta_0 |}{1 + \sum_k (r_k + \varphi) \rho_k}. \quad (26)$$

663 Nonlinear projections on the GML

664 In Fig. 4 and Supplementary Fig. 1, we delve into the effects of introducing heterogeneity in environmental settings
665 and its impact on shaping the GML. Our exploration is centered around three key variations.

666 The first variation pertains the noise intensities Fig. 4a-c. We linearly map items to their ranks considering
667 higher sensory noise associated with higher serial position k according to the linear relation $\sigma_S(k) = \sigma_S(1) +$
668 $\beta(k - 1)$. The network used has $N = 100$ units. Sensory noise was modulated according to $\sigma_S(1) = 0.0075$
669 and corruption rate β ranging from 0.0075 to 0.12 (doubling at each increment). Learning and testing trials were
670 100 per item. Statistics were collected from 100 independent simulations. For violin plots, data are collected from
671 10000 simulations for both the learning and testing phases.

672 The second variation involves the number of learning trials in which a specific item of the sequence appears
673 (Supplementary Fig. 1). This presentation schedule eventually leads to the number of learning trials decreasing
674 with the serial position k of the item as $N_L(k) = N_L(1) - \beta_N(k - 1)$. The network size is the same, and the
675 sensory noise during the testing phase is $\sigma_S = 0.3$, with β_N ranging from 2 to 5. Statistics were collected from
676 100 independent simulations.

677 The third variation focuses on a probabilistic reward schedule in the transitive inference task Fig. 4d-f. For
678 each learning trial (couples with symbolic distance $|\text{SD}| = 1$), the reward for a correct answer is given based on
679 a probability that is higher for higher ranks. Specifically, given a couple of symbols $\{S_k, S_{k+1}\}$, the probability of
680 receiving a reward is calculated as:

$$P_{\text{reward}}(r_k, r_k \pm 1) = \text{CDF} \left(-\frac{\log(1 \mp 1/r_k)}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right), \quad (27)$$

681 where CDF is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution, and σ is the scaling factor
682 of the reward schedule. This approach is equivalent to considering the response target for a trial $\{S_k, S_{k+1}\}$ as
683 the sign of a random value η extracted from a Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(-\log(1 \mp 1/r_k), \sqrt{2}\sigma)$. For this pair of
684 items the rewarded scenario corresponds to $\eta > 0$ (right motor choice). The probability that a Gaussian random

685 variable $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$ is positive is given by $\text{CDF}(\mu/\sigma)$, leading to Eq. (27). Note that $1 - \text{CDF}(-\mu/\sigma) = \text{CDF}(\mu/\sigma)$
686 so that the same reward probability holds for both pairs $\{S_{k+1}, S_k\}$ and $\{S_k, S_{k+1}\}$. Even in this case, the network
687 size is $N = 100$, and the number of learning and testing trials per pair was 10000. σ ranged from 0 to 0.35.

688 Dimensionality analysis

689 Fig. 8 depicts the outcomes of the principal component analysis (PCA) conducted on the network activity sim-
690 ulated during the testing phase of the task. To perform PCA, the sampling matrix $T \times N$ is initially centered at
691 zero by subtracting its time averages. In this context, T represents the number of time steps of the test phase
692 and N stands for the number of nodes in the network. Subsequently, the associated covariance matrix and its
693 eigenvectors, which embody the principal components, are computed. Notably, the network state projected onto
694 the eigenvector with the maximum eigenvalue is the projection onto the first principal component.

695 Data availability

696 The data generated in this study can be recreated by running the publicly available code as described in the Code
697 availability statement.

698 Code availability

699 All codes are available at <https://github.com/gdianto/GeometricMentalline>.

700 Acknowledgments

701 We are deeply indebted to E. Brunamonti and S. Ferraina for having introduced us to the transitive inference
702 task and for the many stimulating discussions. Work partially funded by EU H2020 Research and Innovation
703 Programme, Grant 945539 (HBP SGA3) and by the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), M4C2,
704 NextGenerationEU (Project IR0000011, CUP B51E22000150006, 'EBRAINS-Italy') to MM. Preliminary results of
705 this work have been presented in [91, 92].

706 References

- 707 [1] Gordon D Logan. Serial order in perception, memory, and action. *Psychol. Rev.*, 128(1):1, 2021.
- 708 [2] Stanislas Dehaene, Florent Meyniel, Catherine Wacongne, Liping Wang, and Christophe Pallier. The neural
709 representation of sequences: from transition probabilities to algebraic patterns and linguistic trees. *Neuron*,
710 88(1):2–19, 2015. doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2015.09.019.
- 711 [3] Matthew M Botvinick and Takamitsu Watanabe. From numerosity to ordinal rank: a gain-field model of serial
712 order representation in cortical working memory. *J. Neurosci.*, 27(32):8636–8642, 2007. doi: 10.1523/
713 JNEUROSCI.2110-07.2007.
- 714 [4] Yunzhe Liu, Raymond J Dolan, Zeb Kurth-Nelson, and Timothy EJ Behrens. Human replay spontaneously
715 reorganizes experience. *Cell*, 178(3):640–652, 2019.
- 716 [5] Steven M Frankland and Joshua D Greene. Concepts and compositionality: in search of the brain’s language
717 of thought. *Annu. Rev. Psychol.*, 71:273–303, 2020. doi: 10.1146/annurev-psych-122216-011829.
- 718 [6] Zeb Kurth-Nelson, Timothy Behrens, Greg Wayne, Kevin Miller, Lennart Luetzgau, Ray Dolan, Yunzhe Liu,
719 and Philipp Schwartenbeck. Replay and compositional computation. *Neuron*, 111(4):454–469, 2023. doi:
720 10.1016/j.neuron.2022.12.028.
- 721 [7] Mattia Rigotti, Omri Barak, Melissa R Warden, Xiao-Jing Wang, Nathaniel D Daw, Earl K Miller, and Stefano
722 Fusi. The importance of mixed selectivity in complex cognitive tasks. *Nature*, 497(7451):585–590, 2013.

- 723 [8] Valerio Mante, David Sussillo, Krishna V Shenoy, and William T Newsome. Context-dependent computation
724 by recurrent dynamics in prefrontal cortex. *Nature*, 503(7474):78–84, 2013.
- 725 [9] Stefano Fusi, Earl K Miller, and Mattia Rigotti. Why neurons mix: high dimensionality for higher cognition.
726 *Curr. Opin. Neurobiol.*, 37:66–74, 2016. doi: 10.1016/j.conb.2016.01.010.
- 727 [10] Yang Xie, Peiyao Hu, Junru Li, Jingwen Chen, Weibin Song, Xiao-Jing Wang, Tianming Yang, Stanislas
728 Dehaene, Shiming Tang, Bin Min, and Liping Wang. Geometry of sequence working memory in macaque
729 prefrontal cortex. *Science*, 375(6581):632–639, 2022. doi: 10.1126/science.abm0204.
- 730 [11] Yoshua Bengio, Aaron Courville, and Pascal Vincent. Representation learning: A review and new perspec-
731 tives. *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, 35(8):1798–1828, 2013. doi: 10.1109/TPAMI.2013.50.
- 732 [12] T. Trabasso and C. A. Riley. On the construction and use of representations involving linear order. In
733 Robert L. Solso, editor, *Information Processing and Cognition: The Loyola Symposium*, pages 381–410.
734 Lawrence Erlbaum, 1975.
- 735 [13] Wim Fias, Jean-Philippe van Dijck, and Wim Gevers. Chapter 10 - how is number associated with space?
736 the role of working memory. In Stanislas Dehaene and Elizabeth M. Brannon, editors, *Space, time and*
737 *number in the brain*, pages 133–148. Academic Press, San Diego, 2011. ISBN 978-0-12-385948-8. doi:
738 10.1016/B978-0-12-385948-8.00010-4.
- 739 [14] Mario Bonato, Marco Zorzi, and Carlo Umiltà. When time is space: Evidence for a mental time line. *Neurosci.*
740 *Biobehav. Rev.*, 36(10):2257–2273, 2012. doi: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2012.08.007.
- 741 [15] Regina Paxton Gazes, Victoria L Templer, and Olga F Lazareva. Thinking about order: a review of com-
742 mon processing of magnitude and learned orders in animals. *Anim. Cogn.*, 25, 2022. doi: 10.1007/
743 s10071-022-01713-6.
- 744 [16] Herbert S Terrace, Lisa K Son, and Elizabeth M Brannon. Serial expertise of rhesus macaques. *Psychol.*
745 *Sci.*, 14(1):66–73, 2003. doi: 10.1111/1467-9280.01420.
- 746 [17] Greg Jensen. Serial learning. In *APA handbook of comparative psychology: Perception, learning, and*
747 *cognition, Vol. 2*, APA handbooks in psychology®, pages 385–409. American Psychological Association,
748 2017. ISBN 1-4338-2352-7 (Hardcover); 1-4338-2353-5 (Digital (undefined format)); 978-1-4338-2352-7
749 (Hardcover); 978-1-4338-2353-4 (Digital (undefined format)). doi: 10.1037/0000012-018.
- 750 [18] F Rosenblatt. The perceptron: a probabilistic model for information storage and organization in the brain.
751 *Psychol. Rev.*, 65(6):386–408, 1958. doi: 10.1037/h0042519.
- 752 [19] Daniel J. Amit. *Modeling Brain Function*. Cambridge University Press, 1989. doi: 10.1017/
753 CBO9780511623257.
- 754 [20] Wael F Asaad, Gregor Rainer, and Earl K Miller. Neural activity in the primate prefrontal cortex during
755 associative learning. *Neuron*, 21(6):1399–1407, 1998. doi: 10.1016/S0896-6273(00)80658-3.
- 756 [21] Natasha Sigala, Makoto Kusunoki, Ian Nimmo-Smith, David Gaffan, and John Duncan. Hierarchical coding
757 for sequential task events in the monkey prefrontal cortex. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 105(33):11969–74,
758 2008. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0802569105.
- 759 [22] C Daniel Salzman and Stefano Fusi. Emotion, cognition, and mental state representation in amygdala and
760 prefrontal cortex. *Annu. Rev. Neurosci.*, 33(33):173–202, 2010. doi: 10.1146/annurev.neuro.051508.135256.
- 761 [23] Omri Barak, Mattia Rigotti, and Stefano Fusi. The sparseness of mixed selectivity neurons controls the
762 generalization-discrimination trade-off. *J. Neurosci.*, 33(9):3844–56, 2013. doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.
763 2753-12.2013.
- 764 [24] Paul A M Dirac. *The principles of quantum mechanics*. Oxford University Press, London, iv edition, 1958.
- 765 [25] Carl van Vreeswijk and Haim Sompolinsky. Chaos in neuronal networks with balanced excitatory and in-
766 hibitory activity. *Science*, 274(5293):1724–6, 1996.

- 767 [26] Maurizio Mattia and Paolo Del Giudice. Population dynamics of interacting spiking neurons. *Phys. Rev. E*,
768 66(5 Pt 1):051917, 2002. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevE.66.051917.
- 769 [27] Greg Jensen, Yelda Alkan, Fabian Muñoz, Vincent P Ferrera, and Herbert S Terrace. Transitive inference in
770 humans (*Homo sapiens*) and rhesus macaques (*Macaca mulatta*) after massed training of the last two list
771 items. *J. Comp. Psychol.*, 131(3):231–245, 2017. doi: 10.1037/com0000065.
- 772 [28] Olga F Lazareva. Transitive inference in nonhuman animals. In *The Oxford handbook of comparative cogni-*
773 *tion.*, pages 718–735. Oxford University Press, New York, NY, US, 2012. ISBN 9780195392661.
- 774 [29] Fabian Munoz, Greg Jensen, Benjamin C Kennedy, Yelda Alkan, Herbert S Terrace, and Vincent P Ferrera.
775 Learned representation of implied serial order in posterior parietal cortex. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1):1–14,
776 2020.
- 777 [30] Marco Vasconcelos. Transitive inference in non-human animals: an empirical and theoretical analysis. *Behav.*
778 *Processes*, 78(3):313–34, 2008. doi: 10.1016/j.beproc.2008.02.017.
- 779 [31] Craig Leth-Steensen and Anthony A J Marley. A model of response time effects in symbolic comparison.
780 *Psychol. Rev.*, 107(1):62–100, 2000. doi: 10.1037/0033-295X.107.1.162.
- 781 [32] Tom Verguts and Filip Van Opstal. A delta-rule model of numerical and non-numerical order processing. *J.*
782 *Exp. Psychol. Human. Percept. Perform.*, 40(3):1092–1102, 2014. doi: 10.1037/a0035114.
- 783 [33] Bernard Widrow and Marcian Edward Hoff. Adaptive switching circuits. Technical report, Stanford Electronics
784 Laboratories, Stanford University, Stanford, 1960.
- 785 [34] John A Hertz, Anders Krogh, and Richard G Palmer. *Introduction to the theory of neural computation*. West
786 view Press, Boca Raton, 1991. ISBN 0201515601.
- 787 [35] R Rescorla and A R Wagner. A theory of Pavlovian conditioning: Variations in the effectiveness of rein-
788 forcement and non-reinforcement. In A H Black and W F Prokasy, editors, *Classical conditioning II: Current*
789 *research and theory*, pages 64–99. Appleton-Century-Crofts, New York, NY, 1972.
- 790 [36] Richard O Duda, Peter E Hart, and David D Stork. *Pattern classification*. John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY,
791 2nd edition edition, 2001.
- 792 [37] F Robert Treichler and Debra Van Tilburg. Concurrent conditional discrimination tests of transitive inference
793 by macaque monkeys: List linking. *J. Exp. Psychol. Anim. Behav. Process*, 22(1):105–117, 1996. doi:
794 10.1037//0097-7403.22.1.105.
- 795 [38] Emiliano Brunamonti, Valentina Mione, Fabio Di Bello, Pierpaolo Pani, Aldo Genovesio, and Stefano Fer-
796 raina. Neuronal modulation in the prefrontal cortex in a transitive inference task: Evidence of neuronal cor-
797 relates of mental schema management. *J. Neurosci.*, 36(4):1223–1236, 2016. doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.
798 1473-15.2016.
- 799 [39] Greg Jensen, Yelda Alkan, Vincent P Ferrera, and Herbert S Terrace. Reward associations do not explain
800 transitive inference performance in monkeys. *Sci. Adv.*, 5(7), 2019. doi: 10.1126/sciadv.aaw2089.
- 801 [40] Valentina Mione, Emiliano Brunamonti, Pierpaolo Pani, Aldo Genovesio, and Stefano Ferraina. Dorsal pre-
802 motor cortex neurons signal the level of choice difficulty during logical decisions. *Cell Rep.*, 32(4):107961,
803 2020. doi: 10.1016/j.celrep.2020.107961.
- 804 [41] Michael Page and Dennis Norris. The primacy model: a new model of immediate serial recall. *Psychological*
805 *review*, 105(4):761, 1998.
- 806 [42] Alan D Baddeley. How does acoustic similarity influence short-term memory? *The Quarterly Journal of*
807 *Experimental Psychology*, 20(3):249–264, 1968.
- 808 [43] Adam Drewnowski and Bennet B Murdock. The role of auditory features in memory span for words. *Journal*
809 *of Experimental Psychology: Human Learning and Memory*, 6(3):319, 1980.

- 810 [44] G A Miller. The magical number seven plus or minus two: some limits on our capacity for processing
811 information. *Psychol. Rev.*, 63:81–97, 3 1956.
- 812 [45] A Baddeley. The magical number seven: still magic after all these years? *Psychol. Rev.*, 101:353–6, 1994.
813 doi: 10.1037/0033-295x.101.2.353.
- 814 [46] Stephen Grossberg. Behavioral contrast in short term memory: serial binary memory models or parallel
815 continuous memory models? *J. Math. Psychol.*, 17:199–219, 1978.
- 816 [47] Richard N A Henson. Short-term memory for serial order: the start-end model. *Cogn. Psychol.*, 36:73–137,
817 1998.
- 818 [48] Bruno B Averbeck, Matthew V Chafee, David a Crowe, and Apostolos P Georgopoulos. Parallel processing
819 of serial movements in prefrontal cortex. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 99:13172–7, 2002. doi: 10.1073/pnas.
820 162485599.
- 821 [49] Richard N A Henson, Dennis G Norris, Michael P A Page, and Alan D Baddeley. Unchained memory: Error
822 patterns rule out chaining models of immediate serial recall. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*,
823 49:80–115, 1996. doi: 10.1080/713755612.
- 824 [50] Majid Manoochehri. Up to the magical number seven: An evolutionary perspective on the capacity of short
825 term memory. *Heliyon*, 7, 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06955.
- 826 [51] D R Cox and H D Miller. *The theory of stochastic processes*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1965.
- 827 [52] Joshua I Gold and Michael N Shadlen. The neural basis of decision making. *Annu. Rev. Neurosci.*, 30:
828 535–74, 2007. doi: 10.1146/annurev.neuro.29.051605.113038.
- 829 [53] Bettina D Acuna, Jerome N Sanes, and John P Donoghue. Cognitive mechanisms of transitive inference.
830 *Exp. Brain Res.*, 146(1):1–10, 2002. doi: 10.1007/s00221-002-1092-y.
- 831 [54] David Sussillo, Mark M Churchland, Matthew T Kaufman, and Krishna V Shenoy. A neural network that
832 finds a naturalistic solution for the production of muscle activity. *Nat. Neurosci.*, 18(7):1025–33, 2015. doi:
833 10.1038/nn.4042.
- 834 [55] Rafael Yuste. From the neuron doctrine to neural networks. *Nature reviews neuroscience*, 16(8):487–497,
835 2015.
- 836 [56] H B Barlow. Possible principles underlying the transformation of sensory messages. In W A Rosenblith,
837 editor, *Sensory Communication*, pages 217–34. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 1961.
- 838 [57] Eero P Simoncelli and Bruno A Olshausen. Natural image statistics and neural representation. *Annu. Rev.*
839 *Neurosci.*, 24(1):1193–1216, 2001. doi: 10.1146/annurev.neuro.24.1.1193.
- 840 [58] Matthew G Perich, Juan A Gallego, and Lee E Miller. A neural population mechanism for rapid learning.
841 *Neuron*, 100(4):964–976.e7, 2018. doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2018.09.030.
- 842 [59] Saurabh Vyas, Matthew D Golub, David Sussillo, and Krishna V Shenoy. Computation through neural popu-
843 lation dynamics. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*, 43:249, 2020.
- 844 [60] Mikio C Aoi, Valerio Mante, and Jonathan W Pillow. Prefrontal cortex exhibits multidimensional dynamic
845 encoding during decision-making. *Nature neuroscience*, 23(11):1410–1420, 2020.
- 846 [61] Jintao Sheng, Liang Zhang, Chuqi Liu, Jing Liu, Junjiao Feng, Yu Zhou, Huinan Hu, and Gui Xue. Higher-
847 dimensional neural representations predict better episodic memory. *Sci. Adv.*, 8(16):eabm3829, 2022.
- 848 [62] Jennifer Stiso, Christopher W Lynn, Ari E Kahn, Vinitha Rangarajan, Karol P Szymula, Ryan Archer, Andrew
849 Revell, Joel M Stein, Brian Litt, Kathryn A Davis, et al. Neurophysiological evidence for cognitive map
850 formation during sequence learning. *Eneuro*, 9(2), 2022.

- 851 [63] Nikolaus Kriegeskorte and Rogier A Kievit. Representational geometry: integrating cognition, computation,
852 and the brain. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 17(8):401–412, 2013.
- 853 [64] SueYeon Chung and LF Abbott. Neural population geometry: An approach for understanding biological and
854 artificial neural networks. *Current opinion in neurobiology*, 70:137–144, 2021.
- 855 [65] M R D’Amato and M Colombo. The symbolic distance effect in monkeys (cebus apella). *Animal Learning &
856 Behavior*, 18(2):133–140, 1990.
- 857 [66] H Davis. Transitive inference in rats (rattus norvegicus). *J. Comparative Psychol.*, 106(4):342–349, 1992.
- 858 [67] HS Terrace. A nonverbal organism’s knowledge of ordinal position in a serial learning task. *Journal of
859 Experimental Psychology: Animal Behavior Processes*, 12(3):203, 1986.
- 860 [68] Jeffery A Dusek and Howard Eichenbaum. The hippocampus and memory for orderly stimulus relations.
861 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 94(13):7109–7114, 1997.
- 862 [69] Greg Jensen, Fabian Munoz, Anna Meaney, Herbert S Terrace, and Vincent P Ferrera. Transitive inference
863 after minimal training in rhesus macaques (*Macaca mulatta*). *J. Exp. Psychol. Anim. Learn. Cogn.*, 47(4):
864 464–475, 2021. doi: 10.1037/xan0000298.
- 865 [70] F Robert Treichler, Mary Ann Raghanti, and Debra N Van Tilburg. Serial list linking by macaque monkeys
866 (*macaca mulatta*): list property limitations. *Journal of Comparative Psychology*, 121(3):250, 2007.
- 867 [71] S Ramawat, V Mione, F Di Bello, G Bardella, A Genovesio, P Pani, S Ferraina, and E Brunamonti. Differ-
868 ent contribution of the monkey prefrontal and premotor dorsal cortex in decision making during a transitive
869 inference task. *Neuroscience*, 485:147–162, 2022.
- 870 [72] Olga F Lazareva and Edward A Wasserman. Transitive inference in pigeons: Measuring the associative
871 values of stimuli b and d. *Behavioural Processes*, 89(3):244–255, 2012.
- 872 [73] Stanislas Dehaene and Jacques Mehler. Cross-linguistic regularities in the frequency of number words.
873 *Cognition*, 43(1):1–29, 1992.
- 874 [74] Stanislas Dehaene. Varieties of numerical abilities. *Cognition*, 44(1-2):1–42, 1992.
- 875 [75] Charles R Gallistel and Rochel Gelman. Preverbal and verbal counting and computation. *Cognition*, 44(1-2):
876 43–74, 1992.
- 877 [76] Tom Verguts, Wim Fias, and Michaël Stevens. A model of exact small-number representation. *Psychonomic
878 bulletin & review*, 12:66–80, 2005.
- 879 [77] Stanislas Dehaene. The neural basis of the weber–fechner law: a logarithmic mental number line. *Trends
880 Cogn. Sci.*, 7(4):145–147, 2003.
- 881 [78] Daniel Algom. The Weber–Fechner law: A misnomer that persists but that should go away. *Psychol. Rev.*,
882 128(4):757–765, 2021. doi: 10.1037/rev0000278.
- 883 [79] Herbert S Terrace. The simultaneous chain: a new approach to serial learning. *Trends Cogn. Sci.*, 9(4):
884 202–10, 2005. doi: 10.1016/j.tics.2005.02.003.
- 885 [80] Dharshan Kumaran and James L McClelland. Generalization through the recurrent interaction of episodic
886 memories: a model of the hippocampal system. *Psychological review*, 119(3):573, 2012.
- 887 [81] Stephanie Nelli, Lukas Braun, Tsvetomira Dumbalska, Andrew Saxe, and Christopher Summerfield. Neural
888 knowledge assembly in humans and neural networks. *Neuron*, 111(9):1504–1516, 2023.
- 889 [82] Samuel Lippl, Kenneth Kay, Greg Jensen, Vincent P Ferrera, and LF Abbott. A mathematical theory of
890 relational generalization in transitive inference. *bioRxiv*, pages 2023–08, 2023.
- 891 [83] Greg Jensen, Herbert S Terrace, and Vincent P Ferrera. Discovering implied serial order through model-free
892 and model-based learning. *Front. Neurosci.*, 13:1–24, 2019. doi: 10.3389/fnins.2019.00878.

- 893 [84] Larry F Abbott and Carl van Vreeswijk. Asynchronous states in networks of pulse-coupled oscillators. *Phys.*
894 *Rev. E*, 48(2):1483–1490, 1993.
- 895 [85] Alessandro Treves. Mean-field analysis of neuronal spike dynamics. *Network*, 4(3):259–84, 1993.
- 896 [86] Nicolas Brunel and Vincent Hakim. Fast global oscillations in networks of integrate-and-fire neurons with low
897 firing rates. *Neural Comput.*, 11(7):1621–71, 1999. doi: 10.1162/089976699300016179.
- 898 [87] Bruce W Knight. Dynamics of encoding in neuron populations: some general mathematical features. *Neural*
899 *Comput.*, 12(3):473–518, 2000.
- 900 [88] Herbert Jaeger and Harald Haas. Harnessing nonlinearity: predicting chaotic systems and saving energy in
901 wireless communication. *Science*, 304(5667):78–80, 2004. doi: 10.1126/science.1091277.
- 902 [89] Alfonso Renart, Jaime de la Rocha, Péter Barthó, Liad Hollender, Néstor Parga, Alex Reyes, and Kenneth D
903 Harris. The asynchronous state in cortical circuits. *Science*, 327(5965):587–90, 2010. doi: 10.1126/science.
904 1179850.
- 905 [90] Gianni V Vinci, Roberto Benzi, and Maurizio Mattia. Self-consistent stochastic dynamics for finite-size net-
906 works of spiking neurons. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 130(9):097402, 2023. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.130.097402.
- 907 [91] Gabriele Di Antonio, Sofia Raglio, and Maurizio Mattia. Ranking and serial thinking: a geometrical solution.
908 In *Bernstein Conference 2022*, Berlin, 2022. Bernstein Network. doi: 10.12751/nncn.bc2022.205.
- 909 [92] Sofia Raglio, Gabriele Di Antonio, Emiliano Brunamonti, Stefano Ferraina, and Maurizio Mattia. Learning
910 to infer transitively: ranking symbols on a mental line in premotor cortex. In *2022 Neuroscience Meeting*
911 *Planner*, volume Program No. 564.19, San Diego, CA, 2022. Society for Neuroscience.